

~70 Years of India and Japan Diplomatic Relations~
*~United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable
Development (2021-2030)~*

ABSTRACTS

12th ISAJ Annual Symposium - 2021

Hybrid mode (in-person and online)

Science-Technology-Innovation Towards A Sustainable World

November 26– 27, 2021

**Tokai University Marine Science
Museum (Auditorium)**

Dr. Kedar Mahapatra, Convener

Dr. Swapnil Ghodke, Co-convener

Dr. Santosh Gothwal, Co-convener

Dr. Manjiri Kulkarni-Deshpande, Co-convener

Indian Scientists Association in Japan

Indian Scientists Association in Japan

特定非営利活動法人

(NPO Reg. No. 0503-05-001817)

<http://www.isaj.org>

ISAJ is registered as a Japanese non-profit organization (NPO) under Japan's NPO law. Tsukuba has been decided to be ISAJ's headquarter. The Executive Body is ISAJ's governing body and is responsible for directing the affairs and determining the future of the society. The Executive Body will appoint some of the Executive Body members to take responsibilities such as the Chapter Presidents of six different regions in Japan (Hokkaido, Tohoku, Tokyo, Tsukuba, Fukuoka, and Osaka).

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The Ambassador of India to Japan

Honorary Advisor:

Counsellor (Science & Technology), Embassy of India, Japan

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Ambassador of India to Japan

Chairman, ISAJ

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के. विजयराघवन

भारत सरकार के प्रमुख वैज्ञानिक सलाहकार

K. VijayRaghavan

Principal Scientific Adviser to the Govt. of India

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Message

It gives me great pleasure to know that the Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ) is organizing its 12th Annual Symposium on Nov. 26-27, 2021, at Tokai University Marine Science Museum (Auditorium) in Shizuoka City of Japan.

I have known ISAJ from my previous interactions. I believe that Japan is a special place to learn and perform. With its unique social and work culture, and world leadership in technologies, it offers special opportunities for young generation to excel in professionalism that is well marked with politeness and patience. I have observed these characteristics in Indian scientists who are trained in Japan. DAILAB is one of the role models of international collaborations.

With rapidly changing world in terms of environment and population dynamics, there are new challenges to face for sustainability of natural resources. Japan has excelled in infrastructure technologies and is a world leader in disaster prevention sciences and innovation. Ocean health is an issue to which the whole world, and Japan in particular, is rapidly building strength. This year is of special importance as we are celebrating the 70th Anniversary of India-Japan Diplomatic Relations. I see that ISAJ has selected multidisciplinary theme of *Science-Technology Innovation Towards Sustainable World* this year and will have a one-day program dedicated to Ocean Sciences. This is very timely and appreciable as an event related to already announced *United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021-2030)*. I am happy to see that the symposium will address such frontier and multidisciplinary topics in science and technology and focus on Quality of Life.

I congratulate ISAJ and the members of its symposium organizing committee for having strengthened this association over the years and strengthening India-Japan S&T Cooperation in a variety of ways. I wish the symposium a grand success.

(K. VijayRaghavan)

Dated : 15th November, 2021

भारत के राजदूत
AMBASSADOR OF INDIA

भारत का राजदूतावास
Embassy of India
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Tokyo 102 0074

MESSAGE

I am happy to extend my best wishes to the Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ) for its Twelfth Symposium at Tokai University, Shizuoka on November 26-27, 2021.

The Embassy has supported ISAJ since its inception. It is a forum that enables young Indian researchers and students to gain a broader perspective by connecting with scientists and research institutions in Japan. This year's theme is aptly titled "*Science and Technology Innovation (STI) towards a Sustainable World*". The theme has a great relevance to contemporary issues both in India and Japan and I believe that the new knowledge derived and exchanged among the disciplines and across the institutions would help finding innovative solutions for some of the challenges faced by the humanity and the environment.

I sincerely hope that the Indian and Japanese scientific fraternity would take full advantage of the unique platform of ISAJ.

I am sure that the scientific deliberations during the symposium would lead to constructive recommendations for enhancing strategic partnership between the two countries.

I wish the Symposium a grand success.

(Sanjay Kumar Verma)

Tokyo
9 November 2021

On behalf of the ISAJ, we would like to take this opportunity to welcome all the delegates and guests to the 12th Annual Symposium of Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ). The theme of this year's symposium is "Science-Technology-Innovation Towards a Sustainable World." ISAJ, a Non-profit Organization (NPO), was conceived in 2008 as a community forum by coming together of many Indian scientists working in Japan, and formally inaugurated by Dr. R. Chidambaram, the then Principal Scientific Adviser to the Government of India, in the presence of His Excellency Hemant Krishan Singh, the then Ambassador of India, in January 2009. It has come a long way since then. Registered as a NPO in Japan in 2010, ISAJ has been functioning to promote seminars, community discussions, and networking at all levels: from undergraduate students to academic/industrial professionals. This bridging function has connected many scientists and researchers, helped several young Indian students to get professional training and experience in Japan, and has played successful role in India-Japan Science & Technology cooperation.

Annual symposium has been a highlight of ISAJ activities continuously for the past 11 years. We are proud to celebrate its 12th anniversary today. As in every year, the symposium, is planned to highlight the research being carried out by Indian researchers and their colleagues in Japan. Every year, we have had large participation from multidisciplinary fields. The first seven symposia were held at the main auditorium of the Embassy of India in Tokyo, followed by the eighth one in Tokyo University campus, the ninth in AIST Tsukuba campus, and for the tenth, it moved to the Kansai region, the Osaka university campus. Last year, the 11th Annual Symposium was held online due the COVID pandemic but breaking physical barriers. We are happy to meet again this year in a hybrid mode (on-site and online) at Shimizu, Shizuoka City, thanks to the generous hosting by the Tokai University.

As in the previous years, we have maintained the interdisciplinary pattern of the symposium, offering opportunity to many participants for exchange of ideas and experiences. Through the scientific contents of the presentations over the years, the diverse and expanding scientific and technological areas in which the Indian researchers are working in Japan is clearly visible. It can also be observed that over the years more and more of Indian researchers are moving up as young researchers and faculty in Japan, as well as moving to positions in prestigious universities in India.

This year, we have selected the theme: "Science-Technology-Innovation Towards a Sustainable World". As a first year of *United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021-2030)*, we are honored to host this symposium at the auditorium of the Tokai University Marine Science Museum. Ocean science is an integral part of our life. Climatic changes have been

affecting the ocean ecosystem to a large extent, and it is extremely important to innovate thoughts and technologies for sustainability of ocean resources in a best possible way.

This year marks **70 years of India-Japan Diplomatic Relations**. There is no better way to celebrate it than the present symposium, which symbolizes and exhibits the scientific exchanges between our two countries.

We take this opportunity to welcome our guests and are looking forward to intense interactions. Young researchers' presentations have been the highlight of our earlier symposia and continue to be so this year. We also look forward to hearing from the senior scientists on their long-term experiences working in Japan and positive contributions towards India-Japan science and technology cooperation. We sincerely believe that this is a unique opportunity for all of us to interact and learn beyond our daily activities and our specialized roles in research. We have no doubt that coming together on this platform will benefit young Indian students and researchers in several ways.

Our gratitude to His Excellency Mr. Sanjay Kumar Verma, Ambassador of India to Japan and Dr. Usha Dixit, Science and Technology Counsellor, and other dignitaries for joining us for the 12th annual symposium. We are sincerely thankful to all our guests for contributing to the event with their participation. We sincerely hope that we all will enjoy the symposium and make best of this excellent opportunity to interact with each other and strengthen India-Japan S&T ties with new friendships and collaborations.

With best regards,

Sunil Kaul
Chairman, ISAJ

Alok Singh
Vice-Chairman, ISAJ

Message from the Conveners

We, the conveners, would like to warmly welcome our esteemed guests and all participants, both in-person and online, to the 12th ISAJ Annual Symposium (Hybrid) on “Science-Technology-Innovation (STI) Towards A Sustainable World” being organized on the 70 years of India-Japan diplomatic relations and the First Year of the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021-2030). We very much appreciate the guidance and generous help extended to us by the Tokai University as the co-organizer through the School of Marine Science and Technology, Institute of Oceanic Research and Development, Graduate School of Oceanography, Graduate School of Science and Technology, and Graduate School of Earth and Environmental Science. We also value the support and encouragement received from the Embassy of India and the City Government of Shizuoka for this epoch-making event to become a reality.

After the prolonged restriction on interaction platforms of the scientific conferences due to the COVID-19 outbreak, it is our great pleasure to be organizing the 12th ISAJ Annual Symposium in hybrid mode. We congratulate all our participants and are truly grateful for their serious interest in exchanging research work at the Symposium. We are happy to announce that the hybrid format of the Symposium attracted an overwhelming number of abstracts for both in-person and online presentations, the largest in the 12-year history of the Symposium, including keynote, plenary, invited lectures, besides short presentations by the young scientists, and almost one-third of them will be presented in person. Furthermore, we are encouraged to have the participants from institutes across Japan and outside Japan: India, South Korea, Indonesia, Germany, etc., being submitted to the Symposium. As another first, from this year, the ISAJ has introduced two honorary awards as (1) ISAJ Lifetime Achievement Award (2) ISAJ Distinguished Mentor Award to be presented in the inaugural session of the Symposium. We would like to thank the members of the Symposium Organizing Committee for extending their unstinted support, which enabled us to achieve this new record.

It is our sincere wish that this Symposium gives you a little bit of extra energy to keep on going with your research work in these difficult times. Please enjoy all the presentations during this 2-day event. Thank you, and welcome again!

 Dr. Manjiri Kulkarni-Deshpande			
Convener	Co-convener	Co-convener	Co-convener

12th Annual ISAJ Symposium

70 years of India and Japan Diplomatic Relations

United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021-2030)

Science-Technology-Innovation (STI) Towards A Sustainable World

Tokai University Marine Science Museum (Auditorium)

(Interdisciplinary and Hybrid)

Time (JST)

DAY 1: Nov. 26, 2021 (Friday)

11:30-13:30 Registration (Beach Hotel Gosea's Lobby)

Inaugural Session

14:00-14:04	Opening Address	Dr. Kedar Mahapatra, Convener, the 12th Annual ISAJ Symposium
14:04-14:08	Welcome Address	Prof. Hiroshi Saito, Dean, School of Marine Science and Technology, Tokai Univ.
14:08-14:13	Chairman's Address	Dr. Sunil Kaul, Chairman, ISAJ
14:13-14:23	Inaugural Address	H.E. Mr. Sanjay Kumar Verma, Ambassador of India to Japan
14:23-14:28	Chancellor's Address	Prof. Kiyoshi Yamada, Chancellor, Tokai University
14:28-14:33	Mayors' Address	Mr. Nobuhiro Tanabe, Mayor, Shizuoka City
14:33-14:38	Counsellor's Address	Dr. Usha Dixit, Counsellor (S&T), Embassy of India, Tokyo
14:38-14:43	Special Address	Mr. Yoshiro Kaku, Chief Representative, NEDO, India
14:43-14:48	Awards Presentations & Addresses	ISAJ Life Time Achievement Award Distinguished Mentor Award
14:48-15:18	Keynote Lecture	Prof. Asahiko Taira, Executive Director, Institute of Oceanic Research & Development, Tokai University <i>"Comparison of the Tectonic Framework between Eastern India and Southwestern Japan -Implications for the Evolution of Continental Crust- F53"</i>
15:18-15:23	Vote of Thanks / Closing Remarks	Dr. Alok Singh, Vice-Chairman, ISAJ

Group Photo

15:23-15:28

Tea Break

Ocean Science & Technology (Plenary and Invited Lectures)

Chairs: Satoshi Ishikawa, Tokai Univ. and Swadhin Behera, JAMSTEC

15:50-16:10	Plenary Lecture (Web)	Towards Blue Economy. <i>Shailesh Nayak, Director, National Institute of Advanced Studies, India</i>
16:10-16:30	Plenary Lecture	Oceans for a Sustainable World. <i>Swadhin Behera, JAMSTEC</i>
16:30- 16:50	Invited Lecture	Experimental Study on Applicability of Molten Slag to Tidal Flat Materials. <i>Masato Niki, Tokai University</i>
16:50- 17:10	Invited Lecture	Negative pressure effect plate for portable underwater robot. <i>Norimitsu Sakagami, Tokai University</i>
17:10 -17:25	Invited Lecture (Web)	Surface layer temperature inversion, a rare oceanographic process occurring in the Kuroshio-Oyashio frontal zone and the northeastern Indian Ocean(Southeastern Arabian and Bay of Bengal). <i>Pankajakshan T, Naval Physical & Oceanographic Laboratory (NPOL), India</i>
17:25-17:40	Invited Lecture (Web)	Escalating levels of pathogenic Fecal Indicator Bacteria in coastal waters and marine beaches of Mumbai, India: a public health risks. <i>Abhay B. Fulke, National Institute of Oceanography, India</i>
17:40-17:55	Invited Lecture (Web)	Effects of climate variability on pelagic fishery production in the Indian Ocean. <i>Jonson Lumban-Gaol, Institut Pertanian Bogor (IPB) University, Indonesia</i>
17:55-18:00	Closing Remarks	<i>Satoshi Ishikawa, Tokai University</i>

Time (JST)	DAY 2: Nov. 27, 2021 (Saturday)	
8:30 9:15	Registration: (Beach Hotel Gosea's Lobby)	
9:15 9:30	Convener's opening remarks: Swapnil Ghodke & Santosh Gothwal	
9:30 10:50	Session 1- Plenary ROOM A (Marine Science Museum Auditorium) <i>Session Chair: Swadhin Behera & Sunil Kaul</i>	
9:30 9:50	The state of climate and its future projection in IPCC AR6 (WG1) Prabir K. Patra, JAMSTEC (in person)	
9:50 10:10	Design of Microstructures in Metallic Materials for High Performance and Reliability Alok Singh, NIMS (in person)	
10:10 10:30	Optimum Preparation Methods of Poly(vinyl alcohol) Gels with Excellent Swelling and Mechanical Properties Atsushi Suzuki, Yokohama National University (in person)	
10:30 10:50	Smart Windows for Energy Savings and Emerging Technologies utilizing Vanadium Dioxide Films with Insulator-Metal Transition Kunio Okimura, Tokai University (in person)	
10:50 11:00	Break	
	Session 2	
11:00 12:15	Session 2A	Session 2B
	ROOM A (Marine Science Museum Auditorium) <i>Session Chair : Rumpa Pal & Usha Dixit</i>	ROOM B (Beach Hotel Gosea's Lobby) <i>Session Chair: Santosh Gothwal</i>
11:00 11:15	Living cell manipulation and analysis using nanoneedle Chikashi Nakamura, AIST (In person)	Why is REM sleep important? Deependra Kumar, University of Tsukuba (web)
11:15 11:30	Definitions of reality and the role of scientists in science and technology for a sustainable world: Emphasis on Japan activities and influence of the United States Darius C. Greenidge, Shizuoka University (In person)	Protective Effects of Ashwagandha Extracts on Palmitate Acid-Induced Lipid Accumulation and Oxidative Stress in Hepatocytes Dongyang Li, AIST (web)
11:30 11:45	Selective Separation of Medically Indispensable Isotope Gases through Nanopores Sanjeev Kumar, Shinshu University (In person)	Ashwagandha Withanolides Enhance Muscle Cell Differentiation Jia Wang, AIST (web)
11:45 12:00	π -hole Bonding in a New Co-crystal Hydrate of Gallic Acid and Pyrazine: Static and Dynamic Charge Density Analysis Rumpa Pal, University of Tsukuba (In person)	Cancer Targeted Delivery of Withaferin A Using a Nanostructured Covalent Organic Framework Yu Yue, AIST (web)
12:00 12:15	Therapeutic Taping Technique (Hatanaka Style) Catherine E Shukla, Shukla Hatanaka medical taping center (In person)	CRISPR-based Genome Editing Tools for Basic and Applied Biological Research Rahul Shelake, Gyeongsang National University, Korea (web)
12:15 13:15	Lunch Break (Beach Hotel Gosea's Lobby) and Poster Session (Marine Science Museum Auditorium)	
12:15 13:15	Poster session: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Two Snailfishes of the Genus <i>Osteodiscus</i> (Scorpaeniformes: Liparidae) from Japanese Waters, Kenta Murasaki, Tokai University How can we maintain the "Richness" of agriculture? Focus upon the Utilization and protection of heirloom crops in Shizuoka, Kuniko Hanamori, Tokai University Covid-19 impact on Collaboration between University Students and Local Community, Hiyori Nagano, Tokai university Evaluation of the carotenoid contents heirloom sweet potato 'ninjin-imo', Setsuko Maeda, Shizuoka Professional University of Agriculture Remote sensing in coastal water monitoring: Applications in the Suruga Bay and the coastal waters along the east coast of Japan, Kedarnath Mahapatra, Tokai university 	

Session 3 - Young Researchers		
13:15-14:05	Session 3A	Session 3B
	ROOM A (Marine Science Museum Auditorium) <i>Session Chair: Manjiri Kulkarni</i>	ROOM B (Beach Hotel Gosea's Lobby) <i>Session Chair: Abhay B Fulke</i>
13:15 13:20	Cell Surface Engineering with Functional Peptides to Improve Therapeutic Effect for Stroke Treatment Isha Goel, The University of Tokyo (web)	microRNA-708 Regulates CARF (a stress regulatory protein) Differentially in Telomerase Positive and Negative Human Cancer Cells He Huifu, AIST (web)
13:20-13:25	How can we maintain the "Richness" of agriculture? Focus upon the Utilization and protection of heirloom crops in Shizuoka Kuniko Hanamori, Tokai University (web)	Antistress and Antiaging Activities in Lipoic Acid: Experimental Evidence Ashish Kaul, DAILAB, AIST (web)
13:25 13:30	Covid-19 impact on Collaboration between University Students and Local Community Hiyori Nagano, Tokai university (web)	Anti-Stress Activities in the Hypoxia-Inducing Phytochemical Tectorigenin Mallika Khurana, DAILAB, AIST (web)
13:30 13:35	Evaluation of the carotenoid contents heirloom sweet potato 'ninjin-imo' MAEDA Setsuko, Shizuoka Professional University of Agriculture (web)	MortaparibPlus - A Novel Multimodal Anticancer Small Molecule Anissa Nofita Sari, DAILAB, AIST (web)
13:35 13:40	Mortaparibmild: A Novel Anticancer Agent with p53-dependent and -independent Mechanism Hazna Noor Meidinna, DAILAB, AIST (web)	Cell-based Screenings for Anti-stress Natural Compounds: Selection of Ashwagandha Withanolides and Their Molecular Mechanisms Huayue Zhang, University of Tsukuba (web)
13:40 13:45	Isolation and Characterization of 3-Chlorobenzoate (3-CB) Degrading Bacteria from Soils in Shizuoka Ifat Ara, Shizuoka University (web)	Use of sequencing batch reactor for simultaneous carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus removal from domestic wastewater by alternatng cyclic times Vinod Kumar Jangam, IIT BHU, India (web)
13:45 13:50	Stress Buffering and Longevity Effects of AE in Caenorhabditis elegans (C. elegans) Somuah-Asante, Sandra, University of Tsukuba (web)	Geospatial assessment of expanding solar farms for electrification of India Hitesh Supe, Hokkaido University (web)
13:50 13:55	Developing a Low-Cost Open-Source based UAV System for Mapping of Plantations Land Use in Sabah, Malaysian Borneo. Stanley Anak Suab, Hokkaido University (web)	Machine learning based approach for assessment of typhoon induced forest damage in case of Hokkaido Xinyu Chen, Hokkaido University (web)
13:55 14:00	Isolation and Identification of Indigenous Chromium Tolerant Bacteria from a Heavy Metal Polluted Urban Creek, India Aashna Monga, National Institute of Oceanography (NIO), India (web)	Capturing and transmission of drug resistance gene by conjugative plasmids Singh Shweta, Shizuoka University (web)
14:00 14:05		Study of Geo-morphological changes in Chambal Ravine of India using TanDEM-X SAR and machine learning model Raveena Raj, Hokkaido University (web)
14:05 14:15	Break	

Session 4		
14:15-14:30	Session 4A	Session 4B
	ROOM A (Marine Science Museum Auditorium) <i>Session Chairs :Saurabh Singh & Swapnil Ghodke</i>	ROOM B (Beach Hotel Gosea's Lobby) <i>Session Chair: Santosh Gothwal</i>
14:15-14:30	Various programs for graduate study and collaborative research at NIMS Seiji Kuroda, Global Networking Division, NIMS (web)	Long lead predictions of ENSO using convolutional neural networks Kalpesh Ravindra Patil, JAMSTEC (web)
14:30-14:45	Strategic Interfacial Design for Advanced Secondary Batteries Noriyoshi Matsumi, JAIST (web)	Synthesis, Characterization and Molecular Docking Study of Isoxazolines Swarnagowri Nayak, Manipal Institute of Technology, India (web)
14:45-15:00	Design of ideal active sites on the ZrO ₂ surface in the anode layer to improve SOFC performance Shigeharu ITO, NIMS (web)	Molecular Mechanism of Apical Hook Development in Arabidopsis thaliana Pawan Kumar Jewariya, Beijing Forestry University, China (web)
15:00-15:15	Emerging Materials for Mitigating the Environmental Threats Rajendra P Bunkar, Defense R & D Establishment (DRDE), India (web)	On elucidation of structure-function relationship of human proteins upon binding with sulfa drugs Jhimli Bhattacharyaa, NIT Nagaland (web)
15:15-15:30	Opportunities and challenges in the search of highly efficient thermoelectric materials Sudhir Kumar Pandey, IIT Mandi, India (web)	Development of Novel DNA Aptamer-based Analytical Tools to Detect Toxic Insecticides from Plants Ulhas S. Kadam, Gyeongsang National University, Republic of South Korea (web)
17:30-17:45	Design and Development of Mechanically Robust p-Type Thermoelectric Device Using Flexible Ag ₂ (S,Se) Material Saurabh Singh, Toyota Technological Institute (web)	CRISPR/Cas9-mediated Genome Engineering of Tomato for Pathogen Resistance Trait: A Case Study Dibyajyoti Pramanik, Gyeongsang National University (web)
15:45-16:00	Break	

Session 5		
16:00-17:30	Session 5A	Session 5B
	ROOM A (Marine Science Museum Auditorium) <i>Session Chairs :Saurabh Singh & Swapnil Ghodke</i>	ROOM B (Beach Hotel Gosea's Lobby) <i>Session Chair : Rumpa Pal & Manjiri Kulkarni</i>
16:00-16:15	Cell surface engineering with heparin-conjugated lipids for regulating blood activation in transplantation Yuji Teramura, AIST (In person)	Response Surface Based Model Updating of Heritage Multiple Arch Gallery Masonry Bridge Vinay Shimpi, National Institute of Technology Puduchery, India (web)
16:15-16:30	Subsurface mapping using ground penetrating radars (GPR) Elvis Anup Shukla, Ehime University, Imeiyu GK (In person)	Application of High-Performance Computing to Fire Safety Assessment of Reinforced Concrete Structures Mahendra Kumar Pal, IIT BHU, India (web)
16:30-16:45	Highly respirable SWCNT based stretchable sensor for skin CO ₂ gas monitoring Preety Ahuja, Shinshu University (In person)	Nanoparticle Functionalized with Biomolecular Machines PK Hashim, Hokkaido University (web)

Session 5 Continued.....

16:45 17:00	Detection and evaluation of specific single cell by using "magcup" Hyonchol Kim, DAILAB, AIST (In person)	Numerical and Experimental Investigation of Slow-Drift Damping for a Single-Point Moored Floating Offshore Wind Turbine Sharath Srinivasamurthy, Saga University (web)
17:00 17:15	Marine small-scale fisheries in Cambodia Leakhena Chin, Tokai University (Web)	Experiments and Numerical Analysis on Wave Energy Converter using Ocean Breaking Waves Paresh Halder, Saga University (web)
17:15 17:30	Assessment of marine litter and microplastics (MPs) quantification along the Indian coast Pravakar Mishra, National Centre for Coastal Research, India (web)	Accurate classification of breast cancer cells from normal mammary epithelial cells by machine learning assisted Raman microspectroscopy Hemanth Noothalapati, Shimane University (web)
17:30 17:40	Sperm allocation strategies in Japanese pygmy squid Ryohei Tanabe, Tokai University (In person)	
17:40 18:00	Closing Ceremony and Award Session	

Abstracts

Day 1

**Comparison of the Tectonic Framework between
Eastern India and Southwestern Japan
-Implications for the Evolution of Continental Crust-**

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In the global plate tectonic context, eastern India and the surrounding areas from the Himalayas, Myanmar, and the Nicobar-Andaman Sea region, represent a typical continent-continent collision zone to submarine fan sedimentation/accretion and back-arc basin formation. Likewise, from the Suruga-Nankai Trough to the Rukyu Trench-Okinawa Trough areas in Japan also represent an active arc-arc collision zone to trench-turbidite sedimentation/accretion and back-arc basin formation. In both cases, important processes related to the upper continental crust evolution are involved. The Izu-Bonin arc is the place where juvenile proto-continental crust has been formed and at the collision zone with the Honshu off-scraping of andesitic upper-middle crust is taking place. The erosion of collisional mountain ranges (the Japan Alps) supplies the turbidites to the plate boundary (the Suruga-Nankai Trough) and being accreted to form a secondary crust made of mostly recycled materials. In the Himalayas, the collision of the Indian subcontinent against the Lasa continental block produced a fold-thrust belt involving former continental margin sedimentary wedge (Tethyan sediments) and a metamorphic belt of lower continental crust affinity. The denudation of the Himalays has produced a huge submarine sedimentary body (Bengal Fan) which has been subducted and partly accreted at the Nicobar Trench to form an accretionary wedge. Back-arc basins are the sites of continental crust rifting and extension, hydrothermal activity, sedimentary filling, and hydrocarbon formation. This comparative overview of the plate tectonic schemes of both India and Japan provides a simplified yet useful understanding of the classification and evolution of upper part of continental crust: (1) ocean island arcs and their collision belt (greenstone-granite belt), (2) turbidite accretionary belt, (3) fold-thrust belt of continental margin sediments and basement rocks, (4) continental crust extension and basin filling and (5) igneous intrusives, extrusives and cover sequences. Time-space evolution and relative role of the above-listed 5 categories provide a first-order insight to the history of continental crust and global environmental changes.

Towards Blue Economy

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In this century the focus is on 'oceans' as it provides us energy, food and mineral resources as well as an ecosystem to survive. Blue economy is essentially an ocean dependent economic development for improving quality of life of people as well as ensuring environmental and ecological security. The major Issues are, sustainable use of living resources and non-living resources (minerals, hydrocarbons, water), utilisation of renewable energy, shipping and port development and eco-friendly tourism. The assessment of hazards and development of response mechanism (cyclone, tsunami, sea level rise, coastal erosion, etc.) are critical for protecting infrastructure and saving lives of people. Sustained and systematic observation and information on world oceans, especially for physical, biogeochemical, biological and ecological parameters. are needed. Ecosystem based models are to be developed to manage competing demands and maintaining healthy state of ecosystems as well as to assess impacts of human activities including climate change. Policy framework, governance structure, both international and national (EEZ, CLCS, CRZ, etc. International waters) are to be worked out. The responsible stewardship of oceans is an investment that will pay dividends for generations to come. We need to renew our commitments to oceans especially to ensure sustainability of coasts and oceans and thus the planet Earth, for the benefit of mankind.

Oceans for a Sustainable World

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Oceans have played a vital role in the evolution of life on earth. As human society evolved it became increasingly dependent on oceans for various needs from food to recreation and from cheap transportation to rare minerals. Oceans are also a part of the global climate system that affect not only human beings but also all other lives on earth. Considering its paramount importance on our lives and the earth's environment it is very important that we understand the processes through which it interacts with atmosphere, land, ice and most importantly the ecosystem. Over the years, oceans have stored a lot of heat that was generated as a consequence of the anthropogenic changes on earth. As a result, the oceans are warming up. The estimated increase in heat content represents a volume mean warming of 0.09°C of the 0-2000m layer of the World Ocean, which is equivalent to an approximate warming of 36°C for the lower 10 km of the global atmosphere. While the oceans are warming rapidly, the distribution of the warming is not necessarily uniform over the globe. And that non-uniformity is going to affect differently the modes of climate variations such as the El Niño/Southern Oscillation (ENSO), the Indian Ocean Dipole and ENSO Modoki. Since these climate phenomena directly or indirectly affect weather and climate in many parts of the world, it is important for us to correctly understand their evolution in future climate. These climate phenomena also affect the marine ecosystem in many parts of the World Oceans. For example, El Niño and positive IOD are shown to cause coral bleaching in the Pacific and Indian Oceans. Those impacts are going to be even more under the stress of global warming.

Ocean circulation systems are important for heat transportations from tropical regions to polar regions and thereby maintaining the present climate system. Any change in the circulation systems might add to the woes of global warming. They are also important to study the distribution of marine plastic debris, which has become a global concern now.

The sustainability of the oceans and their environments are vital for the sustenance of human lives on earth. Bi-lateral and multilateral corporations are needed to understand global as well as regional issues. JAMSTEC has been working together with the Ministry of Earth Sciences and other institutions in India to address some of the issues in the Indo-Pacific sector through collaborative studies. We hope those studies will contribute to the sustainable development of our world under the auspices of the UN Decade of Ocean.

Experimental Study on Applicability of Molten Slag to Tidal Flat Materials

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The melting furnace is a disposal treatment method that melts, reduces, and detoxifies general waste from households. The melting furnace in Shizuoka City melts at ultra-high temperatures between 1700°C and 1800°C by adding coke. As a result, dioxins are practically non-existent. After melting, "molten slag," a detoxified substance similar to sand, is discharged. This molten slag is not only recycled as a raw material for roadbed material and concrete, but is also used as fertilizer. To improve the environment of coastal areas, industrial by-products such as steel slag are being used. Molten slag is rarely used for the improvement of the environment in coastal areas. In this presentation, the results of creating artificial tidal flats using molten slag and investigating the effects on water quality and benthic habitat will be presented.

The comparative experiment was conducted in the FRB (Fiber Reinforced Plastics) water tank to clarify the effect of molten slag to seawater quality and its performance as habitat material for benthos. Four pairs of two tanks were set up, and each pair was filled with molten slag, silica sand, a mixture of silica sand and molten slag, and gravel. "Asari clams" were then added to one of the pairs, and the tanks were constantly supplied with natural seawater. The experiment was conducted for about 3 months and was carried out 4 times. In the first experiment, the water quality was examined for a week immediately after the seawater was supplied. In a similar experiment using steel slag, the value of pH was sometimes above 9 even after 100 days, but in the molten slag tank of this study, pH was the same as that of the seawater after 3 hours. The value of COD (Chemical Oxygen Demand) or the concentration of heavy metals of concern for human health has not been increased. Since then, the water quality was checked once a month. Monthly water quality monitoring indicated that the pore water of the slag-filled tanks measured higher phosphorus than seawater. It was suggested that the molten slag could adsorb or re-elution phosphorus. Since there was no difference in the death rate of the added clams, this indicates that molten slag has potential as a material for tidal flat.

Negative pressure effect plate for portable underwater robot

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In recent years, many types of small and lightweight underwater robots have been released and used for actual monitoring and inspection. However, such small and lightweight robots have low-power thrusters. Their positioning performance during free-floating is poor under external disturbances. Additionally, it is difficult for untrained operators to control the robot position in three dimensions.

To overcome control difficulties and to improve maneuverability, we introduce a negative pressure effect plate (NPEP). The NPEP attached to a thruster can generate negative pressure induced by thruster water flow and can thereby generate a strong pulling force between an underwater robot and a surface of underwater structures. Using the pulling force, the NPEP offers stable positioning of an underwater robot on underwater structures and provides easy command control for operators and observers.

Surface layer temperature inversion, a rare oceanographic process occurring in the Kuroshio-Oyashio frontal zone and the northeastern Indian Ocean (Southeastern Arabian and Bay of Bengal)

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Surface layer temperature inversion (SLTI), a warm layer sandwiched between surface and subsurface colder waters, has been reported to frequently occur in conjunction with barrier layers in the Kuroshio-Oyashio frontal zone and the northeastern Indian Ocean (Southeastern Arabian and Bay of Bengal), with potentially commensurable impacts on climate. In both these regions, this oceanographic process occurs during the winter and is limited to the surface layer of about 100 meters. In the northwest Pacific, when the cold Oyashio current meets the warm Kuroshio current, a temperature inversion occurs in the frontal zone of these two currents. Whereas, in the northeastern Indian Ocean (the Arabian Sea and Bay of Bengal), the advection of low saline surface water and winter cooling act as the causative factors. The low salinity is induced in this region by the freshwater dumping from the major rivers (Ganges, Brahmaputra, Krishna, Godawari, etc.) and excess precipitation over evaporation.

Escalating levels of pathogenic Fecal Indicator Bacteria in coastal waters and marine beaches of Mumbai, India: a public health risks

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Global estimates indicate that each year more than 120 million cases of gastrointestinal disease and 50 million cases of severe respiratory diseases are caused by swimming and bathing in wastewater-polluted coastal waters. The unregulated disposal of wastes and other materials into the ocean degrades marine and natural resources and pose human health risk. Hence, study was conducted to investigate the presence of pathogenic *Escherichia coli* Fecal Indicator Bacteria (FIB) in anthropogenically marred beaches and coastal waters of Mumbai, India. Out of 316 presumptive *E. coli* isolates, 118 were found to be pathogenic *E. coli* which was subjected to serotyping and antibiotic susceptibility test. The presence of virulence genes specific to diarrheagenic pathotypes namely EHEC, EPEC, ETEC and STEC were determined using a molecular approach. Diarrheagenic pathotypes ETEC and EPEC were found to be predominant among the studied sites. 100% of the isolates were Multiple Antibiotic Resistant with higher MAR indices. Therefore, coastal ecosystem and beach management should be implemented to ensure possible associated public health risk.

Effects of climate variability on pelagic fishery production in the Indian Ocean

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Climatic dynamics such as the Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD) on the marine environment determine the distribution, migration, and abundance of the pelagic fish. As a result, the impact of climate variability on the fisherfolk-livelihood is likely to be significant. We reviewed the effects of climate variability on the distribution and abundance of pelagic fish in the Indian Ocean. Climate dynamics affect the abundance of both small and large pelagic fish. During the positive (negative) phase of the IOD, the abundance of pelagic fish increased (decreased) in the Eastern Indian Ocean (EIO), and vice versa occurred in the Western Indian Ocean (WIO). The variability in fish production during positive and negative phases was influenced by an intensive upwelling (downwelling) process during the positive (negative) phase of the IOD in both the eastern and western Indian Ocean.

Day 2

Session 1: Plenary

The state of climate and its future projection in IPCC AR6 (WG1)

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The Working Group I of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) has prepared the most up-to-date physical understanding of the climate system and climate change in its Sixth Assessment Report (AR6). The report shows that the Earth's global surface air temperature has increased by 1.07°C in the period 1850-1900 to 2010-2019. This global warming is attributed to the rise in greenhouse gases, such as carbon dioxide (CO₂), concentration due to the human activities (Fig. 1). The report shows unprecedented changes in the climate and predicts increase in extreme heat, heavy rainfall, drought and forest fires, ocean acidification and deoxygenation, sea-level rise etc. The panel calls for strong, rapid and sustained reductions in CO₂, methane (CH₄) and other greenhouse gases to limit global warming.

Figure 1: The present understanding of the global carbon cycle. The time series plot at the centre show how human produced (anthropogenic) CO₂ emissions have changed in the period 1960-2019 (red line) along with the fraction of the anthropogenic emissions that is remaining in the atmosphere (symbols and black line; number on the top). The anthropogenic emissions are produced mainly by consumption of fossil-fuels and forest clearing for residential and agricultural purposes, as shown on the right. The natural ecosystems on land and oceans are removing part of the anthropogenic emissions as depicted on the left, which has slowed the build up of CO₂ in the atmosphere in the past.

Design of Microstructures in Metallic Materials for High Performance and Reliability

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We depend crucially on metallic materials for most part of our daily lives –buildings, transport vehicles, electronic devices, or power plants situated far away. Often these materials are working at extreme performance limits or environments such as jet engines, power plants and spacecrafts. Advanced engineering of these materials keeps them reliable, and our lives safe, while getting high performance from them.

In this talk we will look at the structures and microstructures inside these materials and how can we manipulate these structures to get the functions and performance that we want. We will look at the mechanisms by which these materials get deformed and how we can stop them from deforming. Examples will be given of earthquake-defying steels, “greener” automobiles and in-situ degradable biological implants. We will also look at some exotic metallic materials which need to be described in six-dimensional space.

The lightest of all metallic materials for structural applications are magnesium alloys. Applications of these alloys in automobiles can have huge positive effect on fuel economy and the environment. While such applications are still being worked out by overcoming challenges of mechanical and corrosion properties, magnesium alloys may find promising use as self-degradable medical implants. Magnesium is a commonly available inexpensive metal which is also bio-compatible. Bio-implants of magnesium alloys remove the need for a second surgery, reducing stress on a patient, surgical costs and related human efforts.

Optimum Preparation Methods of Poly(vinyl alcohol) Gels with Excellent Swelling and Mechanical Properties

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The mechanical properties of polymer gels can be controlled by manipulating the microstructure of the polymer networks. The strength of a gel, which is characterized by an equilibrium elastic modulus, is generally proportional to the density of the crosslinks, and the higher the density of crosslinks, the harder the gels. Recently, we reexamined the preparation methods of PVA (poly(vinyl alcohol)) gels, such as conventional preparation methods, such as, a freeze-thawing method, a cast-drying method, and non-frozen isothermal crystallization method. And we succeeded to prepare physically crosslinked PVA (poly(vinyl alcohol)) gels with unique textures, such as multiple-layered, functionally graded, anisotropic structures. These unique textures can be applied to develop novel medical devices.

In this lecture, we present the preparation methods to obtain transparent PVA gels with excellent swelling and mechanical properties by a non-frozen isothermal crystallization method. A PVA solution in an organic solvent–water mixture was quenched from a high temperature, and kept for 24hr at various temperatures between -40 and 60°C . The preparation conditions and the control factors, including the gelation temperature, the standing time, and the mixing ratio of organic solvent and water were systematically changed. As a result, it was found that the transparency can be controlled by changing both the gelation temperature and the standing time. Similarly, the swelling ratio and mechanical properties depended on the control factors of gelation. The optimum conditions of gel preparation were explored to show the high swelling ratio and the mechanical strength with different transparency. By combining the present results with our recent gelation technologies¹⁾, we are aiming to develop the medical devices made of PVA hydrogels, such as for artificial organ phantoms, surgical training models, and so forth.

Reference: 1) A. Suzuki, T. Hara, R. Mochiduki, and H. Abe, PVA Hydrogel and Method for Manufacturing Same, WO/2020/226157 (PCT/JP2020/018558) , 12.11.2020.

Smart Windows for Energy Savings and Emerging Technologies utilizing Vanadium Dioxide Films with Insulator-Metal Transition

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There is a growing interest for environmentally friendly metal-oxide materials. Vanadium dioxide (VO₂) is known as a phase transition compound which shows insulator-metal transition (IMT) with its structural phase transition (SPT) from low-temperature monoclinic phase (P21/c) to high-temperature tetragonal phase (P42/mnm) at 68 °C. The abrupt resistivity change over 4 orders of magnitude is realized even in thin films with thickness of less than 10 nm. The reversible and durable IMT has triggered a lot of studies on VO₂ thin films not only for unravelling the physics of phase transition but also for applications to various engineering field.

We have been fabricating stoichiometric VO₂ thin films by using reactive magnetron sputtering method. By introducing radio-frequency substrate biasing, we succeeded low temperature growth of stoichiometric VO₂ films on various substrates. As one of promising application, we are trying to fabricate VO₂-coated glasses for smart windows where infrared-light (IR) incidence is automatically controlled to avoid room temperature rise in hot summer. Large change of transmittance for IR concomitant with the IMT enabled VO₂-coated glass as smart windows with automatic reduction of IR with temperature rise. As performance index, we realized the solar modulation ability (ΔT_{sol}) of 14.5 % which is world-wide top ranking value, although the luminous transmittance (T_{lum}) of 20% is still rather low. [1-3]

There are some technologies utilizing IMT of VO₂ films such as active metasurfaces for terahertz transmission control [4] and coupled-oscillation device. [5] These emerging technologies will be key issues for next generation information technology (IT) society.

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Session 2A

Living cell manipulation and analysis using nanoneedle

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We have been developing nanoneedles, which are materials made by etching with focused ion beam an atomic force microscope (AFM) probe into a needle shape with a diameter of 200 nm and more than 10 μm in length, as a tool to penetrate into cells. By using AFM, it is possible to observe a process of needle inserting into a cell as force-distance curve with several tens of pico Newtons of force resolution in real time while performing the operation. The success or failure of nanoneedles in penetrating the cell membrane can be observed as the repulsion relaxation on the force curve. We have confirmed that the damage caused by insertion is minimal, and even if the insertion operation is repeated 50 times in the same cell, the doubling time of the cell is not affected at all. Nanoneedles can be used in a variety of ways, such as delivery molecules into cells and detection target substance, intracellular RNAs or proteins. In this talk, I especially introduce the topic of the technology to detect cytoskeletal proteins mechanically.

Definitions of reality and the role of scientists in science and technology for a sustainable world: Emphasis on Japan activities and influence of the United States.

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In this world of ever-growing science and technology that heavily influences the lives of all human beings and the creatures of this planet Earth, it had been stated by the late, dynamic electrical engineering entrepreneur and former professor of Toyama University, Dr. Shoji Ichimura, that the modern scientist can no longer simply be a scientist. He/she must also be an economist, a statesman, and a sociologist in order that we maintain a sustainable world. Nothing can be truer in view of the poorly advised government leaders who often leave a trail of disaster for their countrymen on their way out of office. Yet the problems of our world persist, and it is accentuated here that the well-rounded and noble scientist can have profound influence upon the course of the future of this planet. None may be as equipped as the innovators of Japan and other upcoming nations, and the potential of grand possibilities could be made or broken relative to the direction of technological developments in Japan and the United States. We shall briefly explore the history and future possibilities catalyzed by these two nations with reference to the positive potential development for the rest of the world.

Selective Separation of Medically Indispensable Isotope Gases through Nanopores

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Imagine a basket full of tennis balls, identical in color and size, varying merely by a tenth of a gram in weight. Even with the right equipment, sorting out the heavier tennis balls would likely be a challenging and tedious work. A similar situation exists in separation of isotopes, including oxygen-16 (^{16}O) and oxygen-18 (^{18}O) or carbon-12 (^{12}C), carbon-13 (^{13}C) and carbon-14 (^{14}C) etc., due to their extremely low natural abundance and nearly identical physical and chemical properties. Hence, their separation remains an immense challenge. These isotopes are particularly significant for a wide range of applications including clinical radiopharmaceuticals, in studies of brain disease and most importantly as an imaging probe for advanced medical imaging techniques such as Positron Emission Tomography (PET) for early detection of various types of cancer cells. Therefore, ^{18}O plays an indispensable role for PET diagnosis, however, is difficult to procure because with its very low natural abundance 0.204 at. % compared to the principal ^{16}O (99.76 at. %), its separation is currently only possible with limited techniques, such as cryogenic distillation of oxygen / nitric oxide / water, membrane distillation, isotope exchange reaction, and thermal diffusion. These methods involve complicated equipment, extremely low separation efficiency ($S_{18}/S_{16} \approx 1.046$) and take more than 6 months to complete; which make them extremely energy-intensive and incur high production cost. Subsequently, alternative technologies are essential to meet the increasing demand for oxygen-18 in healthcare and environmental science fields.

Here, we present a novel method and instrument devised for the rapid, less energy-intensive and efficient separation of ^{18}O from ^{16}O , or ^{13}C from ^{12}C . This rapid and preferential adsorption-based separation of ^{18}O resulted in a separation efficiency S_{18}/S_{16} above 60 using nanoporous carbide-derived carbon (CDC) adsorbent, operating near the boiling point of methane (112 K), which is accessible through the low-temperature waste heat from a natural gas storage facility. Similar, high separation efficiency was also evident for the separation of ^{13}C with $S_{13}/S_{12} = 56 \pm 6$. We discovered a cooperative or collective nuclear quantum effect (NQEs), which is different from the well-known translational motion-based quantum molecular sieving (QMS) effect, can explain the high separation efficiency of ^{18}O or ^{13}C by subnanometer pores.

π -hole Bonding in a New Co-crystal Hydrate of Gallic Acid and Pyrazine: Static and Dynamic Charge Density Analysis

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A new cocrystal dihydrate of gallic acid with pyrazine (2GA, Py, 2H₂O; GA₂PyW₂) was obtained and characterized by single crystal X-ray diffraction. In addition to structure determination, experimental charge density analysis was carried out in terms of Multipole Modeling (MP), X-ray Wavefunction Refinement (XWR) and Maximum Entropy Method (MEM).¹ As a part of XWR, the structural refinement via Hirshfeld atom refinement (HAR) was carried out and resulted in O–H bond lengths close to values from neutron diffraction. A systematic comparison of molecular conformations and aromatic interactions in this new cocrystal hydrate was performed with other existing polymorphs of gallic acid. In GA₂PyW₂, the two symmetry-independent gallic acid molecules have a *syn* –COOH orientation and form the common (COOH)₂ dimeric synthon. The carboxyl C atom displays the characteristics of π -holes with electropositive regions above and below the molecular plane and engages in acceptor-donor interactions with oxygen atoms of acidic O–H groups and phenol groups of neighbouring gallic acid molecules (Fig. 1). The signature of the π -hole was identified from experimental charge density analysis, both in static density maps in MP and XWR as well as dynamic density in MEM, but it cannot be pinned down to a specific atom-atom interaction. This study presents the first comparison between an XWR and a MEM experimental electron-density determination.²

Figure 1. (a) parallel stacking dimer1//. The distances for C1...O7 contact is shown. (b) molecular graph obtained from topological analysis of experimental dynamic density from MEM analysis, MPMEM-n2 for dimer1//. (c) 3-dimensional experimental static deformation density obtained from multipole model. Colour code: blue (positive), red (negative)

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Therapeutic Taping Technique (Hatanaka Style)

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The human body is a very fascinating and complex system, where all the organs work in harmony. When this harmony is disturbed, by either external causes or muscular imbalance, it will give rise to pain. There are a number of alternative therapies that claim to be effective in healing the pain, with Taping emerging as one of the new techniques. Taping enhances the natural healing process of the body while providing support to muscles and joints without restricting the body's movement. The Hatanaka style Taping Method is designed to make people heal faster.

We often confuse symptoms with the cause of an alignment as pain and numbness are the symptoms, and the cause often lies in other areas. Even if we treat the symptoms, the cause of the pain stays untreated, and thus pain reoccur. Therapeutic tape, when applied correctly, will lift the skin and increase the subcutaneous space which increases the blood and lymph flow. It also helps to create a balance in the neural circuitry in muscles, tendons, joints, and skin. And this, helps to reduce pain, decrease swelling, and improve muscle performance and function. The way of putting tape over muscles has a direct effect on muscle movement. If applied correctly, one will feel a miraculous improvement in the pain, just like magic. On the other hand, tape applied incorrectly, can deteriorate muscle function. Hatanaka taping style focuses on putting therapeutic tapes unstretched over manually stretched skin above injured muscles.

Taping is a practical approach to live in harmony with nature. This knowledge and practice can be a fantastic way to aid our self-care. Integrating taping knowledge with the elements of Ayurveda and yoga can be a wonderful way to develop a new self-treatment technique that could be helpful for everyone. In Make in India, we are emphasizing creating smart and hi-tech cities, but cities with unhealthy people will not be sustainable. We should add 'Make in Healthy India' project in which one brings alternative medicinal therapy to India from all over the world. This will give an opportunity to young minds to think more seriously about complementary and alternative medicine., with the idea of minimum manipulation of the body with maximum results. This is not in competition with mainstream medicine, but rather moving along with it. To achieve a sustainable world, we also need to have a vision for a sustainable health system, which improves or restores health with a minimum negative impact on the environment and ensures the well- being of current and future generations.

Session 2B

Why is REM sleep important?

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Sleep has two basic types: rapid eye movement sleep (REM) sleep and non-REM sleep. The quality and quantity of REM sleep are generally essential for normal body physiology. However, the specific function of REM sleep is not well understood. This talk will focus on the first thermoregulatory function of REM sleep¹, the second REM sleep role in recovery from stress², and the third memory consolidation function of REM sleep³.

Ambient temperature (T_a) affects not only sleep onset but also sleep quality and quantity⁴. Total sleep time, especially REM sleep, peaks at moderate warm T_a . Peripheral and central warm receptors seem to mediate T_a -related sleep changes. Destruction of warm receptors impairs T_a -related REM sleep increase and physiological and behavioral thermoregulation¹. An increase in REM sleep at moderate warm T_a is thermoregulatory in nature.

Sleep is strongly affected by stress experiences. Depending upon the quality of stress, it promotes either REM or NREM sleep during the stress recovery period. For example, restrain stress has a specific REM sleep-promoting effect and is considered crucial adaptive behavior for recovery. *Cacna1c* knock-out mice, a mice model of stress disorders, show reduced REM sleep recovery response upon restrain stress condition². A failure to REM sleep recovery in *Cacna1c* knock-out mice may increase the risk in the case of repeated or chronic exposure to any challenging conditions.

Sleep is crucial to consolidate memory. REM sleep stage characterized by hippocampal theta rhythms (6- 9Hz) seems to provide a favorable brain state for long-term memory storage. We found that the activity of adult-born hippocampal neurons during REM sleep is critical for the consolidation of memory³.

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Protective Effects of Ashwagandha Extracts on Palmitate Acid-Induced Lipid Accumulation and Oxidative Stress in Hepatocytes

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Ashwaganda (*Withania somnifera*) is a popular ayurvedic herb, trusted for a variety of health benefits in Indian traditional home medicine system. Steroidal lactones, Withaferin A (Wi-A) and Withanone (Wi- N), have been characterized as its major bioactives with a variety of bioactivities. We investigated the effect of Ashwagandha extracts on steatosis and oxidative stress within a cell or organ that often affects liver as non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD).

We prepared extracts from Ashwagandha that varied in their Wi-A and Wi-N content. Cytotoxicity of these extracts on human hepatocytes (Huh-7) was evaluated by cell viability assays. Nontoxic doses were used to treat cells subjected to activated lipid accumulation by palmitic acid (PA). The lipolygenesis was evaluated by Oil Red O, triglyceride (TG) assays and reactive oxygen species (ROS) assays, and the expression of molecules involved in this process.

Four kinds of extracts with different amounts of total withanolides and Wi-A:Wi-N ratio were generated. Cells were treated with PA to induce lipid accumulation. We found that in cells pre-treated with specific Ashwagandha extracts, TG and ROS accumulation were decreased. Of note, sterol regulatory element-binding protein-1c (SREBP-1c), and its downstream effector-fatty acid synthase (FASN), the key regulators of lipogenesis showed downregulation in specific extract-treated cells. Furthermore, the expression of peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor (PPAR) γ , a key factor involved in hepatic lipogenesis, showed decrease in cells treated with some of these extracts. PPAR α , the transcription factor that upregulating fatty acid oxidation was induced by PA treatment related to a beneficial effect in preventing lipotoxicity and decreased in specific extract-treated cells.

In summary, Ashwagandha extracts may provide a useful natural resource with anti-steatosis and anti-oxidative stress activities, maintaining liver health and prevent NAFLD.

Ashwagandha Withanolides Enhance Muscle Cell Differentiation

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Ashwagandha (*Withania somnifera*) is an Indian traditional herb commonly used for enhancing quality of life and has been trusted for rejuvenating and revitalizing properties. Several laboratory and clinical studies have reported the efficacy of Ashwagandha extracts for management of body fat and muscles, improvement of brain function and adaptation to stress. We investigated the differentiation potential and stress tolerance in response to the treatment with Ashwagandha extracts and its major withanolides (withaferin A; Wi-A & withanone; Wi-N) in C2C12 myoblasts. We found that withaferin A and withanone, and Ashwagandha extracts possessing different ratios of these active ingredients have different effects on differentiation of C2C12. Withanone and Withanone-rich extracts caused stronger differentiation of myoblasts to myotubes, de-aggregation of heat and metal stress induced aggregated proteins and activation of autophagy pathways. These results demonstrate the potential of Ashwagandha withanolides for the management of muscle repair and activity.

Cancer Targeted Delivery of Withaferin A Using a Nanostructured Covalent Organic Framework

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Covalent organic frameworks (COFs) are a class of newly emerged crystalline porous materials that possess fascinating features such as porosity, stability, tunability, and biocompatibility. The permanent yet tunable porosity combining with large surface area and low-density structures make COF an ideal drug reservoir.

In this study, we developed a folate receptor-targeting COF by conjugating folate to an amphiphilic COF skeleton of which pore channels are capable for sufficient drug loading. The nanosized COF obtained by simple solvent-assisted sonication was well-dispersed in water and showed high affinity to folate receptor (FR)-positive cancer cells. We selected Withaferin-A (Wi-A) as a model anticancer drug and performed comparative analyses using FR-positive and -negative cells. The results revealed that Wi-A-loading COF exhibited a stronger cell killing activity for FR-enriched cancers both in vitro and in vivo. Moreover, delivery using COF showed reduced systemic toxicity of Wi-A. These results indicate COF-based nanomedicine has great potentials to improve cancer therapy.

CRISPR-based Genome Editing Tools for Basic and Applied Biological Research

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Mutations are the basis of evolution and all genetic variations. Several mutagenesis tools have been developed to introduce mutations that enable the characterization of gene functions and detection of crucial mutations conferring novel traits to plants and animals. Among the recent genome editing (GE) techniques, clustered regularly interspaced short palindromic repeats/CRISPR-associated protein (CRISPR/Cas)-based tools are transforming basic and applied research. The CRISPR/Cas system is engineered for GE applications that include two major components: Cas nuclease and single-guide RNA (sgRNA). CRISPR-based GE tools have become popular due to several user-friendly features, like higher efficiency, low-cost, simple designing, diverse applicability, a wider range for target selection, and the ability to precisely edit the targeted region in a complex genome. Moreover, genetic modifications can be introduced without foreign gene integration, one of the significant advantages of CRISPR-based tools. The expanding CRISPR-based GE toolbox allow plant engineering at DNA, RNA, and protein level, i.e., across the central dogma of molecular biology. CRISPR-based tools enable the gene knockout/knockin, RNA targeting, DNA/RNA imaging, DNA/RNA base editing, targeted random mutagenesis, and prime editing to introduce any desired DNA modification. The rapid research for understanding the fundamental mechanisms and identification of novel genes/functions can be an excellent impetus for higher food production to meet the demand of global population and climate change. Following aspects will be discussed: the history of mutagenesis tools, CRISPR/Cas system and related tools for GE and beyond, GE applications for agriculture, and regulatory aspects of GE products.

Session 4A

Strategic Interfacial Design for Advanced Secondary Batteries

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It has been widely known that interfacial property has dramatic impact on performance of secondary batteries. Generally, solid electrolyte interface (SEI) formed by decomposition of electrolyte is playing a keyrole in electron transfer event during charge-discharge of secondary batteries. In spite of the importance of SEI, strategic design principle for SEI has not been well established because of their undefined nature. In most Li ion secondary battery systems, uncontrolled decomposition of electrolyte both on anode and cathode result in formation of thick SEI layer which results in large internal resistance and poor performance of battery cells.

In recent years, we have developed useful strategy in controlling SEI formation in both anode and cathode sides utilizing rationally designed polymer binder materials (n-type conjugated polymer binders^{1,2} or polymerized ionic liquids³) or additive compound⁴. Under finely-tuned HOMO-LUMO levels of polymer binder materials (or additives), it was possible to control the SEI layer formation on both electrodes, which resulted in significantly improved battery cycling performance. We have recently extended this methodology for design of high capacity silicon based Li ion battery cells as well. Very high discharging capacity of higher than 2000 mAhg⁻¹ has been observed till more than 500 cycles.

We are also investigating effect of organoboron SEI on Li/Na ion secondary batteries^{5,6}. In these systems, high rate charge-discharge was observed, possibly because of organoboron SEI formation. It is interesting to note that such behavior was observed even the case of Na ion secondary batteries in which reducing power of Na is much lesser than Li. Low LUMO level of organoboron electrolyte enabled rational SEI design for Na ion secondary batteries as well.

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Design of ideal active sites on the ZrO_2 surface in the anode layer to improve SOFC performance

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Cermet material which consists of Ni and 8mol% Y_2O_3 stabilized ZrO_2 (8YSZ) have been widely used as the anode of solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs). Recently, first principle simulation in combination with already available data has shown great potential for innovative breakthroughs in SOFC anode materials research. ¹⁾ The simulation results foresee that H_2O molecule formation reaction on the anode can be greatly enhanced if a new active site, which is formed between the 8YSZ particles and the brownmillerite type promoter particles in the anode layer, is designed to maximize the oxygen surface diffusion on the 8YSZ particles. In this study, we evaluated the anode performance by adding $\text{Ba}_2\text{In}_{2-x}(\text{Zn,Zr})_x\text{O}_5$ (BIZZO), $\text{Ba}_2\text{In}_{2-x}(\text{Mg,Zr})_x\text{O}_5$ (BIMZO) or $\text{Ba}_2\text{In}_2\text{O}_5$ (BIO) promoters. Also, the active sites formed by each promoter doping were analyzed using defect structure simulation (source code: GULP).

The IR-free evaluation results showed that the performance of the anode containing 0.2 wt% of BIZZO, BIMZO or BIO was better than that of the conventional anode without promoter at 700°C, refer to Fig.1. Even

though promoters have almost the same constituent elements and crystal structure, there was a difference in their effectiveness. In order to improve the effect of promoter addition on anode performance, the active sites that should be created were investigated by defect structure simulation.

As a result, it was considered that the oxygen vacancies position on the surface of cubic ZrO_2 that activates the anode reaction is preferably the same as that on the surface of C type rare earth oxide such as Y_2O_3 .

Fig1. IR-free polarization characteristics observed for conventional cermet anode and present work anode with BIZZO or BIMZO, Cermet anode: NiO-8YSZ (weight ratio NiO (4) : 8YSZ (1)), cathode: $\text{La}_{0.85}\text{Sr}_{0.15}\text{MnO}_3$, electrolyte: 8YSZ sintered pellet (thickness: 0.5 mm). Cathode side: O_2 gas flow (80 ml min^{-1}), Anode side: humidified H_2 gas (+ 3 % H_2O) flow (80 ml min^{-1}). Operation temperature: 700°C. Dashed line in (a) indicates the level of 54% of power generation efficiency.

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Emerging Materials for Mitigating the Environmental Threats

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Abstract: The significant advancements in the development of various sectors of economy have been achieved but at the cost of huge environmental damage. The atmospheric concentration of carbon dioxide (a major greenhouse gas) has increased massively in the atmosphere mainly due to the anthropogenic effects, which resulted in 1°C rise in the global temperature than the pre-Industrialised level. The global utilisation of CO₂ is also very negligible (<200 mT/year) in comparison with the global CO₂ emissions (> 32,000 mT/ year). In this context the capture of excess CO₂ and subsequently its conversion to value added products (syn gas, methane etc) becomes utmost important in order to curtail the alarming levels in the environment.

Various sorbent systems like monoethanolamines, modulated amine blends, graphene-type materials, activated carbon, zeolites etc. materials have been explored in the literature for the carbon capture. The Oxides of Ni, Ce & Ru, Carbonates K & Na, Dual function materials (DFMs) are also reported for efficient carbon capture along with some process limitations.

The Metal Organic Framework (MOF) materials are found to be quite efficient with a huge futuristic prospectus for the carbon capture & conversion because of their unique structural and functional aspects. These materials are quite efficient for the CO₂ capture at low pressure levels which makes them promising for realistic atmospheric applications. The chemistry along with the mechanistic aspects of carbon capture & conversion shall be dealt in detail in the presentation.

Finally the strategies for engineering of MOF materials in terms of pore size, selectivity and consequently for enhancing the adsorption capacity will be discussed to conclude the presentation.

Opportunities and challenges in the search of highly efficient thermoelectric materials

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The progress of any civilization is directly linked to the amount of energy consumption. Our modern life is fully dependent on different sources of energy we require for daily needs. At present, fossil fuels are the main energy sources, which are limited in stock and main sources of emission of green-house gases. About two-third of the heat generated from fossil fuels gets wasted. This waste heat can be converted into useful energy by using a thermoelectric generator which is fabricated by using thermoelectric materials (TEM). The efficiency of TEM is typically defined by using a dimensionless parameter known as ZT . Higher the value of ZT , the better is the TEM. For TEM with $ZT \sim 1$, one can get an efficiency of $\sim 10\%$, which is quite low in comparison to other energy conversion technology like heat engines. Thus, to make this technology competitive we need materials with quite high values of ZT in a relatively wide temperature range, especially in the high temperature region. Therefore, researchers are trying hard to search for an efficient new TEM by using both experimental and theoretical techniques. However, these techniques have their own merits and demerits. Thus, in this talk we will try to discuss the opportunities and challenges in the search for highly efficient thermoelectric materials by using experimental and theoretical techniques.

Design and Development of Mechanically Robust π -Type Thermoelectric Device Using Flexible $\text{Ag}_2(\text{S},\text{Se})$ Material

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The development of thermoelectric generators for alternate source of energy are currently a major focus as devices capable of supplying an input power (μW to mW) to many sensors, electronic gadgets, and wearable devices in low temperature range around 300 – 400 K [1]. Improvement of figure of merit, ZT , of the thermoelectric materials used in such device are very important. Besides, if these materials are flexible [2], the number of applications would be significantly enlarged. Recently, Ag_2S is found to be an interesting material, as near room temperature it possesses good flexible properties with very low thermal conductivity ($\sim 0.5 \text{ W/m K}$) and large Seebeck coefficients ($\sim -900 \mu\text{V/K}$) [3]. However, due to large electrical resistivity ($\sim 10^6 \text{ m}\Omega \text{ cm}$), the value of ZT was found to be very low. To improve the ZT , the substitutions of Se, Te at sulfur site are investigated [4,5]. Although significant enhancement in ZT is achieved, but, limited to n -type only. Also, the major focus in the literature is on development of prototype devices, which obviously have small output. To achieve the high-performance, π -type TE device have more advantage, where both n and p -type materials with high ZT are used to generate better output power. Here, we have utilized the Bi-Sb-Te based p -type materials together with flexible Ag_2S and $\text{Ag}_2\text{S}/\text{Se}$ in development of π -type device, and achieve the maximum output power density of $\sim 1.525 \text{ mW/cm}^2$

In the present work, Polycrystalline samples were prepared by using standard melting method. Structural characterization of as-prepared powder sample was carried out by using Bruker D8 Advance Cu K_α source, and found to be in single phase. Chemical composition and grain structure analyses were performed using Scanning Electron Microscope-Energy Dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (SEM-EDX), HITACHI SU 6600. Heat and electron transport properties were measured on hot-pressed bulk samples. Thermal conductivity measurement was done by using Laser flash analysis (NETZSCH LFA 457); whereas for Seebeck coefficient and electrical resistivity measurement, experimental systems developed in our laboratory were used [4].

Further, by using the synthesized materials showing high ZT , we developed the optimization conditions of stacked device using integrated sintering process, where single pair, two leg and three-leg device were made. The output performance of these devices at different temperature gradient ($\Delta T = 10 - 50 \text{ K}$) were tested using homemade TE device testing equipment interfaced with LabVIEW program. We succeeded in developing the stacked thermoelectric devices, where the issue of cracks formation at boundary of p and n layer due to brittle nature of Bi-Sb-Te are effectively manage by use of highly flexible and insulating Ag_2S inter-layers. These devices can be fabricated easily using simple hot-press technique, have very compact in size, and exhibit maximum output power of $1678 \mu\text{W}$ at $\Delta T = 50 \text{ K}$. The maximum power density of 1.525 mW/cm^2 of mechanically robust device is very useful for commercial applications. In the JSAP meeting, we will discuss in more details about the fabrication, and high-performance output achieved in silver chalcogenides based TE device.

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Session 4B

Long Lead Predictions of Enso Using Convolutional Neural Networks

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Long-lead forecasts of El-Niño southern oscillation (ENSO) has always been a challenge and important due to its wide implications on the global climate. Although, state-of-the art dynamical models make forecasts of ENSO, but their long-lead prediction skills are observed to be poor. On the other hand, deep learning techniques in the recent past have shown improvements for predicting ENSO. In the present work we attempt to forecast ENSO using convolutional neural networks (CNN) at long-lead up to 23 months leadtime. For training the CNN, three different global oceanic fields were considered as inputs viz. global *sea surface temperature anomalies* (SSTA), *vertically average sub-surface temperature anomalies* (VATA) from 0-300m and the *sub-surface temperature anomalies* (STA) at 50, 100, 150 and 200m depths. The inputs were derived from centennial in situ observation-based estimates (COBE) and Simple Ocean Data Assimilation (SODA) reanalysis data sets at 5°x5° spatial resolution. CNN models were trained on long records of data from 1871 to 1973 (~103 years) and tested on ~30 years of records (1985 to 2015) from Global ocean data assimilation dataset (GODAS), along with its comparison with the forecasts of Scale Interaction Experiment-Frontier ver. 2 (SINTEX-F2). The prediction skills of CNN were judged from *correlation coefficient* (r) and *root mean square error* (RMSE). The skills of CNN ensemble predictions from different experiments outperform the SINTEX-F2 ensemble predictions as shown in Fig. 1. This indicates that accurate long-lead forecasting of ENSO is possible using CNN.

Fig. 1: Prediction skills of the proposed CNN's ensemble against the GODAS and SINTEX-F2 ensemble during peak season (DJF) at 18 months leadtime.

Synthesis, Characterization and Molecular Docking Study of Isoxazolines

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Oral Presentation

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Heterocyclic compounds, having at least one heteroatom play an important role in medicinal chemistry due to their diverse applications, such as anticancer, antimicrobial, antimalarial, antioxidant, anti-HIV, and anti-inflammatory. Also, heterocycles are widely used in material chemistry as fluorescent material, liquid crystals, OLED's etc. Five-membered heterocycles play a major role in medicinal chemistry due to the presence of different reactive sites in it. Among the different five-membered heterocycle, isoxazole is a privileged heterocycle in heterocyclic chemistry and in drug discovery. Presence of isoxazole moiety in various marketed drugs such as Leflunomide, Muscimol, Valdecoxib, and Isoxaflutole encouraged chemists to develop isoxazole derivatives. Prompted by these applications, a series of bezoisoxazole derivatives were synthesized and characterized using FTIR, ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR techniques. All the synthesized compounds were subjected to insilico study to understand the interactions of synthesized molecules with protein. The study revealed that compounds could lead to promising anticancer agents in the future.

Molecular Mechanism of Apical Hook Development in *Arabidopsis thaliana*

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The apical hook develops immediately after seed germination and protects the apical meristem. The asymmetric cell elongation rates (slower elongation on the inner side and faster elongation of outer side) of bending hypocotyl results in formation of hook in dicotyledonous plants. Since apical hook is not required for survival during growth of *Arabidopsis thaliana* seedlings under laboratory conditions, it is an excellent model system to take genetic and cell biological approaches to study mechanisms underlying differential cell elongation. We have focused specifically on the cell wall modification and its role in apical hook development. The *MURI* encodes an enzyme for making GDP-fucose which is required for xyloglucan and RG-II (pectin) biosynthesis. The *mur1* mutant lacks a proper hook and this defect can be rescued by addition of fucose or interestingly, boron. The mobile plant hormone auxin is required for almost every aspect of plant growth and development. The polar transport of auxin is required for proper formation of auxin response maxima and minima for proper plant development. We found that auxin responsive synthetic promoter *DR5::GFP* was decreased in *mur1* background and addition of boron and fucose restored it. Because auxin response maxima is maintained due to polar auxin transport so we checked auxin influx and efflux carriers and we found that specific auxin influx (*AUX1* and *LAX3*) and efflux (*PIN1*, *PIN3*, *PIN4* and *PIN7*) carriers were affected in *mur1* mutant. We also found that inner and outer side cell elongation rate changed in L-fucose deficient *mur1* hook, which results in defective apical hook. We discovered the signal transduction and function of *MURI* in apical hook development. Our study enlightens the molecular mechanism of differential cell elongation in *Arabidopsis thaliana*.

On elucidation of structure-function relationship of human proteins upon binding with sulfa drugs

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Proteins with complex 3D structure, are made up of different amino acids, have multifaceted functions. Their functions are directly connected to their macro structures. Proteins can bind with macromolecules or small molecules/ligands to form giant assemblies. Biophysical interaction studies involving proteins and antibiotic drugs are beneficial to understand the molecular aspects of the association. Here we report the interaction on the sulfa/sulphanilamide (antibiotic) drugs, Sulfamethazine (SMZ) and Sulfadiazine (SDZ) towards human proteins like Hemoglobin (Hb), Myoglobin (Mb), Serum albumin (HSA) via biophysical tools and computational techniques. The binding constants and apparent binding constants, stoichiometry followed by thermodynamic parameters can be obtained from Spectroscopy and Calorimetry. The significant loss in the helicity and the perturbation of the protein structure upon binding with drug were determined by Circular Dichroism (CD), Infra Red and Synchronous fluorescence spectroscopy. The data can be complemented by molecular docking studies. Molecular docking analyses presented best probable binding sites of the drugs into the protein pockets; finally leading to structure-function relationship. Thus the present study explores the potential binding properties of the well known sulfa drugs with proteins, correlating the structural & functional aspects and energetics of the drug-protein interaction.

Keywords: *Proteins, Sulfa drugs, Spectroscopy, Calorimetry, Molecular Docking, Scattering, Thermodynamics*

This work is joint with Mr. Aben Ovung and Miss. A. Mavani, Ph.D Research Scholars, Department of Chemistry, National Institute of Technology Nagaland, Dimapur.

Development of Novel DNA Aptamer-based Analytical Tools to Detect Toxic Insecticides from Plants

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Fenitrothion is an insecticide belonging to the organophosphate family of pesticides, and it is widely used around the world in agriculture and living environments. Today, it is one of the most hazardous chemicals that causes severe environmental pollution. However, detection of fenitrothion residues in the environment is considered a significant challenge due to the small molecule nature of the insecticide and lack of molecular recognition elements that can detect it with high specificity. In this study, we have performed in vitro selection experiments using the SELEX process to isolate the DNA aptamers that bind to fenitrothion. The newly discovered DNA aptamers have a strong ability to distinguish fenitrothion from other organophosphate insecticides (non-specific targets). Furthermore, we identified a fenitrothion-specific aptamer, FenA2, that can interact with Thioflavin T (ThT) to produce a label-free detection mode, with a K_d of 33.57 nM (9.30 ppb) and LOD of 14 nM (3.88 ppb). Additionally, the FenA2 aptamer exhibited very low cross-reactivity with non-specific targets. It is the first report showing an aptamer sensor with a G4- quadruplex like structure to detect fenitrothion. Moreover, these aptamers have the potential to be further developed into analytical tools for real-time detection of fenitrothion from a wide range of samples.

Keywords: Aptamer, SELEX, G4-quadruplex, Thioflavin T, Fluorescence, and Insecticides.

CRISPR/Cas9-mediated Genome Engineering of Tomato for Pathogen Resistance Trait: A Case Study

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Plant diseases are a major threat to global food production. Several plant pathogens, predominantly bacteria, fungi, and viruses, are the root cause of plant diseases, causing significant crop damage and economic losses every year. Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*) is a model dicot plant and one of the most consumed vegetables worldwide. Two major tomato diseases, tomato yellow leaf curl disease and powdery mildew caused by the Tomato yellow leaf curl virus (TYLCV) and the fungal pathogen *Oidium* species hampered tomato cultivation. Effective control of the diseases without perturbing the yield is the researchers' primary concern, and several approaches were taken to solve the problem sustainably. Previous studies suggested that plant susceptibility (*S*-genes) factors can be suitable to engineer and gain stable resistant traits. Wild tomato cultivars carrying the *SIPelo* (*ty5* locus), *S*-allele, encode a messenger RNA surveillance factor, PELO, a crucial player in ribosome recycling during viral protein synthesis. Another *S*-gene, mildew resistance locus *ol* carries the *SIMlo1*, encodes a transmembrane protein MLO1, which is responsible for fungal disease development. Recently discovered, clustered regularly interspaced short palindromic repeats (CRISPR)/CRISPR-associated protein (Cas) is a promising genome engineering tool that can be used to produce disease-resistant crop varieties. In this study, a multiplex CRISPR/Cas9 system was used to engineer the tomato cultivar targeting the *SIPelo*, and *SIMlo1*. After several trials of experiments, *SIPelo*-knockout plants were generated, and viral pathogenicity was evaluated using TYLCV-virulent factor carrying *Agrobacterium*. All the tested *SIPelo*-mutant segregating plants demonstrated decreased viral accumulation and restricted systemic spread of viral factors in plant bio-parts. Likewise, *SIMlo1*-knockout lines were produced that showed stable powdery mildew resistance. Overall, our findings establish the CRISPR/Cas9 system to engineer the tomato genome to develop disease resistance traits.

Session 5A

Cell surface engineering with heparin-conjugated lipids for regulating blood activation in transplantation

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1. Introduction

Ischemia-reperfusion (I/R) injury is one of the most serious problems in organ transplantation. Since the main processes involved in cytotoxic I/R injury are innate immune responses, including coagulation and complement activation. The regulation has been attempted through systemic administration of selected inhibitors. However, the use of systemic regulators has not been particularly effective in inhibiting I/R injury. Also, systemic administration can actually cause side effects such as bleeding and influence other organs' function. Therefore, it is of great importance to protect the cell surfaces from this inflammatory attack in order to achieve successful treatment and a high-level engraftment in organ transplantation. In this study, we propose the new regulator for the I/R injury by applying new concepts of local immune inhibition via cell- surface modification technique¹). Here we synthesized heparin-conjugated phospholipid (heparin-lipid) to mimic glycocalyx, which is lost during I/R injury, and tried to compensate for the damaged glycocalyx with our materials²). We examined the function on the lipid membrane in terms of the complement and coagulation systems.

2. Materials and methods

We synthesized heparin-conjugated lipid by covalently reacting phospholipid and reactive fragmented heparin via Schiff base chemistry in different ratios. We determined the concentration of the amine group using fluorescamine to quantify the conjugated number of fragmented heparin to several lysines-conjugated lipid. Here we changed the heparin conjugation ratio from 1 to 9 per lipid moiety. The properties of the heparin-lipid construct were evaluated by antithrombin-binding using quartz crystal microbalance with energy dissipation (QCM-D), and studied anti-factor Xa activity using modified liposomes. In addition, we evaluated the anticoagulation function of heparin-lipid on human mesenchymal stem cells (hMSC) using human whole blood experiment.

3. Results and discussion

We synthesized heparin-lipid with 0.6, 1.8, 2.7, 4.5, or 8.0 fragmented heparins per lipid to compare their anticoagulation activity. QCM-D study showed that heparin-lipid has strong antithrombin (AT)-binding ability. Furthermore, we could see an increase in the number of AT bindings per heparin-lipid molecule with an increase in the number of fHep conjugated to heparin-lipid, indicating a higher efficiency of AT binding to conjugated fHep with higher density. Then, we modified liposome and cells with each heparin-lipid and evaluated the surface properties. The hemocompatibility of the modified hMSCs was examined in a loop model using human blood. The AT-binding capacity and anti-factor Xa activity of the heparin-lipids depended on the number of conjugated heparins, with efficacy increasing with increasing number of heparins. The modified liposomes were highly negatively charged and showed strong anti-factor Xa activity. In addition, the cell surfaces of hMSCs could be uniformly modified with heparin-lipid. The whole blood studies revealed that heparin-lipid on hMSCs could prevent generation of thrombin-antithrombin complexes, coagulation markers, and platelet aggregation, whereas unmodified hMSCs triggered activation of the platelet and coagulation systems. Thus, our heparin-lipid could be a potent regulator of the coagulation systems, and could thereby function as an artificial glycocalyx during organ transplantation.

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Subsurface mapping using ground penetrating radars (GPR)

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Smart city, hi-tech city, well planned city has well defined surface and subsurface infrastructure. Roads are becoming the very part of these cities these days. Invisible subsurface is also increasing with the increase in the population. The first underground system for water and sewage dates to around 4000 BC, and since then we have constructed innumerable pipes, cables, tunnels, and other constructions below the ground surface.

These are sometimes properly documented with a precise location in both X, Y and Z, but most often the location is unknown or quite diffuse. Over the past century the infrastructure beneath us has changed not only in the broadening nature of materials and construction methods but also in the density of these networks. This increasing complexity translates to an increasing risk for utility strikes, but more important, to an increased risk to people's safety. Roads and infrastructure are susceptible to adverse impact from traffic loads and change in climate. The cracks and potholes which are visible from our eyes are sometimes not the main culprit in road disaster. Sometimes underground cavities which are not visible from our naked eyes causes more damage. Lot of research has been done to enhance the quality of the roads, yet road cracks and potholes are evident. To cope up with these emerging road cavities, proper and precise road survey is needed.

So, what do we do, when we need to extend, renew, and maintain all this subsurface infrastructure? We can use Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR), a well-known technique used in infrastructure exploration. GPR is a non-destructive and rapid geophysical method that works by transmitting electromagnetic waves from an antenna and reflects off layers and objects hidden in the ground. These reflections are collected as data which generates an image of the subsurface. A typical GPR system configuration consists of one or more antenna elements, a control unit, and a monitor or external Tablet/PC, for storage and display of data. The transmitter emits a "train" of electromagnetic impulses which propagate through the media. Reflection (i.e., scattering, echoes) occurs where the electrical properties of subsurface materials change. The receiver picks up the "back-scattered" signal, records it and displays it on the computer screen. GPR system can be single channel that is hand heled or multi-channel that is towed by vehicle.

Highly respirable SWCNT based stretchable sensor for skin CO₂ gas monitoring

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Wearable devices with mechanical deformability are gaining considerable interest in human health monitoring via continuous and noninvasive manner. For instance, stretchable, breathable and soft on-skin sensor which can conformally attached to human skin for transcutaneous administration of carbon dioxide (CO₂) can offer a useful tool for noninvasive evaluation of skin function, microcirculation, metabolism for screening hypercapnia and for continuous monitoring during neonatal intensive care for pulmonary and cardiac disorders. However, established non-dispersive infrared (NDIR) spectroscopy or pH electrode based clinically acceptable CO₂ sensors are rigid and inadequate owing to bulky size, high operating temperature, long response time and frequent calibration. In addition, the sensing electrode materials possess insubstantial gas permeability impeding perspiration evaporation, which adversely effects the physiological conditions and long-term practicability.

Here, an easy, widespread and cost effective approach for fabricating chemiresistive-type stretchable CO₂ sensor using silicone elastomer sponges loaded with amine functionalized single walled carbon nanotube (SWCNT) based composite is reported. The sensor demonstrates high gas and water-vapor permeability which further enhances on stretching, making it compatible for skin-sensor interface. More significantly, the present sensor exhibits a detection limit of 70 ppb CO₂ with excellent reversibility under ambient temperature and humidity and is resilient to the interference of N₂, O₂, CH₄, acetone or NH₃. It displayed stable and reliable response under large tensile strain of 60%, proposing a new insight towards realizing a promising approach for monitoring the skin gas CO₂ for healthcare monitoring.

Detection and evaluation of specific single cell by using "magcup"

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Detection, collection, and evaluation of specific target cells from a cell ensemble are one important topic in life sciences. For example, identification of irregular cells, such as circulating tumor cells, in blood is fundamental to achieving less-invasive health checks. In our previous study, we proposed a method for size-specific target cell collection by using "magcups" [1]. In the method, cup-shaped magnetic hemispheres, magcups, having almost same sizes with cells (10 to 25 μm in diameter) were fabricated, mixed with a cell ensemble, and then target cells were captured into inner concaves of the magcups as size-specific manner. Here, additional two applications of the magcups are presented; one is detection of specific cancer cells by using the cup-shaped biosensors, and the other is evaluation of adhesion strengths in a single cell level by using the cup-attached chip in the atomic force microscopy (AFM).

In the former application, a nano-carbon layer was formed on inner concaves of magcups, and the cups were used as microscopic electrodes. The cup-shaped electrodes were placed on a substrate as an array, marker molecules on cancer cell surfaces were labeled with the ruthenium (a probe molecule of electrochemiluminescence, ECL)-modified antibodies, and the labeled cancer cells were captured to inner concaves of the cup-shaped microelectrodes. After the application of electric voltage, ECL signals were successfully observed from the cancer cell-captured cups with quite high sensitivity.

In the latter application, a magcup was attached to the apex of AFM cantilever. The cup-attached AFM chip (cup-chip) was approached on a cell, and then the cell was picked up by withdrawing the cup-chip such like claw crane game. The cell-attached chip was approached on the other cell, and intercellular adhesion strengths between two living cells were measured [2]. By using this method, intercellular adhesion strengths of cancer cells having different malignancies were evaluated.

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Marine small-scale fisheries in Cambodia

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Cambodian marine fisheries have for many years contributed significantly to the employment and livelihoods of the poor, as well as to food security, the Gross Domestic Product and foreign exchange balance. This study investigates the current status of fishing operation including role of gender in the marine small-scale fisheries of Cambodia. Data/information was collected from 290 fishing households in the six coastal villages of Kampot, Kep, and Preah Sihanouk provinces, using interview questionnaire and focus group discussion. The results indicate that 22 types of fishing methods are operated in the four common fishing areas namely mangrove and tidal flat, along the channel, the ground laying to 10km from the coast, and the outer area of over 10 km from the respective villages, targeting 35 species. There were no differences among the size of fishing vessels use in different types of fishing gears/methods, however, most of trawlers have been operated with large engine power (30-50 Hp). All fishers owned one fishing boat and 80 out of 290 fishers operated two fishing gears for daily household consumption and for commercial purposes. Men, women and children fishers have accessed and used the shorter distance fishing grounds less than 10 km from the shore. Fishers in Chrolong used small boat (5.0-9.5 m in length) to conduct fishing nearby the village within 6.0 km and along the channel. Inshore fishing, stable with low catches would be estimated, whereas large volume with more fluctuation can be observed.

Assessment of marine litter and microplastics (MPs) quantification along the Indian coast

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Plastics are indispensable in modern-day human life and a considerable amount of plastic wastes end up in landfills. Plastic contaminants are widespread, reported from peak Mount Everest to deepest Marina trench, Arctic to the Antarctic and in marine invertebrates to mammals. The mismanaged plastics from the land (source) enter into the ocean via inland waterways find their way into the ocean (sink). The larger plastic particles (Mega, Macro, and Meso) disintegrate due to physical, chemical, and biological weathering into smaller particles (micro and nano plastics). Recently, worldwide, studies on MPs and their quantification, distribution, and toxicity have increased exponentially. At par with the global studies, several studies have been undertaken by Indian researchers. As part of this effort, the Ministry of Earth Sciences (MoES) initiated the program Marine Litter and Microplastics in 2018 aimed to conduct research all along the Indian coast to prepare the National Marine Litter Policies). The main objective of the program is to quantify, assess the distribution pathway from source to sink in different environmental matrices and to create awareness among the public through a citizen science approach

Based on studies available for Indian coasts, MPs range from 0 to 414.35 ± 87.4 items/kg in sediment (54 studies); 8.76 ± 2.11 to 96 ± 57 items/L in water (10 studies); biota 1-69 particle (21 studies) and salt pan (NA to 72 ± 40 items/kg). Studies revealed that the major constituents are polypropylene (PP) of 33% followed by 20 % of polyvinylchloride (PVC). Source identification studies suggest that a major contribution (56 %) is from multiple sources, which could be a combination of two or more sources, followed by 16 % contributed by river runoff. Further, the magnitude of MPs in the coastal region is intensified under the influence of reversal monsoon, wind, and local hydrodynamics regimes. MPs in biota are mostly fibers (elongated), fragments (angular and irregular pieces), films (thin and transparent), and nurdles (round).

Beach litter assessment for Pan India was carried out as a part of International coastal clean-up revealed that single-use plastics (SUPs) are predominant litter (~ 67 %) in the coastal region and tourism and recreational activities contribute about 59% are the major source of the beach litter. Since a majority of the source is land-based SUPs, it is recommended that segregation of waste at source, installing floating barriers at the river mouth, cleaning, monitoring through adopting the beaches by local institutions, raising awareness among the various stakeholders and publics, implementing extended producer responsibility and engaging 3Rs – Reduce, Reuse and Recycle, promoting and regulating unformal sectors by the way of incentives are some of the appropriate options in plastic pollution management.

Keywords: Marine Litter; Microplastics; Source; Sink; India

Sperm allocation strategies in Japanese pygmy squid

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When a female copulates with multiple males, sperm of different males compete to fertilize eggs, which often promotes the evolution of the male's ejaculation strategy. For example, a male of some animals adjusts the ejaculation volume to gain higher fertilization success according to the number of rivals. In the Japanese pygmy squid, males are exposed to strong sperm competition environment, whereas it is unclear whether males adjust their ejaculation volume with the number of rivals. Male squid pass spermatophore to a female. In that time, spermatangium is released from the spermatophore by spermatopholic reaction, and it is attached to the female body (Figure 1). This mechanism allows us to evaluate their ejaculation volume. In this study, we measured the number of transferred spermatangia by the male that is exposed by 0, 1 or 3 rival males presence situation.

The number of rivals did not affect male ejaculation volume (Table 1; figure 2). However, they increased ejaculation volume when mating with bigger females and when males stored a large amount of spermatophore (Figure 3). In addition, they reduce ejaculation volume with their testis size (Figure 3). The previous study shows that females remove spermatangia attached by smaller males after copulation. This behavior is considered to be work for Cryptic Female Choice (CFC). Our results indicate males do not adjust sperm investment with sperm competition risk. However, males seem to adjust their ejaculation volume according to female's and their condition to avoid the risk of sperm removal by female and lacking spermatophore stock.

Table 1: The best five Akaike information criterion (AIC) model of generalized linear mixed models (GLMMs)

Response variable	Explanatory variables	AIC
No. of transferred spermatangium	Female size + TSI + No. of stocked spermatophore	188.8
	TSI + No. of stocked spermatophore	189.7
	Female size + TSI	190.1
	Female size + TSI + No. of stocked spermatophore+ Rival	190.3
	Female size + No. of stocked spermatophore	190.5

*Testicular-somatic index (TSI)

Figure 1: The sperm transfer process in

Japanese pygmy squid

Figure 2 : Number of transferred spermatangium according to number of rivals. A comparison showed no significant differences (GLMMs with Tukey of Number of transferred spermatangium, with number of rivals as fixed effect, and male identity as a random effect; $p > 0.05$). Bars indicate standard error.

Figure 3 : Relationships between number of transferred spermatangium, female size (A), testicular–somatic index (TSI) (B) and number of stocked spermatophore (B).

Session 5B

Response Surface Based Model Updating of Heritage Multiple Arch Gallery Masonry Bridge

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This paper presents a vibration-based model updating procedure for heritage multiple arch gallery bridge of Kalka Shimla Mountain Railway located in the severe seismic zone. The methodology is based on the experimentally identified modal parameters on the Bridge No.541, Kalka Shimla Mountain Railway. In this context, the Finite Element (FE) model of the bridge is generated through visual survey and geometric measurement. Further, the Ambient Vibration Testing and Operational Modal Analysis is performed on the bridge for system identification (dynamic modal parameters). The Response Surface (RS) method is utilised for model updating. In RS method, the central composite design is adopted for the Design of Experiment (DoE) for selected parameters and a quadratic RS model is constructed. Subsequently, the Genetic Algorithm is utilized with an objective function to minimise the differences between experimentally identified natural frequencies and numerically estimated natural frequencies. Finally, the updated FE model of the bridge have good agreement with the field results and hence it is reliable.

Application of High-Performance Computing to Fire Safety Assesment of Reinforced Concrete Structures

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India Risk Survey 2018 had ranked India 3rd in fire incidents, which accounts for approximately 8.45% of overall ranking of risks. The vulnerability of reinforced concrete (RC) structures in the event of fire outbreak is evident in the data of claims of Indian insurance companies which accounts for 45% of total major losses. There are two major challenges in carrying out the assesment of full-sized RC structures, namely, the requirement of large-scale computation infrastrucutres and multi-scaled couple (mechanical+thermal) algorithms for analysis.

National Supercomputing Mission (NSM) eliminates the HPC infrastructures difficulty. The first supercomputer named “Param Shivay” was installed at IIT BHU under NSM scheme, which used more than one lakh twenty thousand compute cores (CPU + GPU cores) to offer a peak compute power of 833 TeraFlops [1]. This facility will be utilized in running the simulation. Akram et. al [2] have developed a mathematical formulation by combing the mechanical stresses with thermal stress using variation approach. The coupled formulation utilizes higher-order particle discretization scheme discretizing the domain and Euler’s forward backward method in discretization of time.

In this talk, author is indedent to talk about formulation of methodology, its verification & validation by simulating the thermal cracking of brittle materials such as ceramic under high-temperature heat. Thermal induced cracking in RC due to high-power heat will also be demonstrated.

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Nanoparticle Functionalized with Biomolecular Machines

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Molecular machines in biology, usually based on proteins, are essential for diverse functions. Hybrid materials of nanoparticle and biomolecular machines are a new class of materials that can potentially integrate high biological functionality of machines with plasmonic properties.¹ However, it is challenging to maintain functional activity of a protein after incorporation onto a nanoparticle. We succeeded in the immobilization of GroEL biomolecular machine onto a AuNP surface (^{GroEL}AuNP) using complimentary DNA strands that were introduced to both GroEL and AuNP (Figure 1). GroEL is a protein refolding machine from chaperonin family that captures denatured protein into its cavities, refold and release the guest by the action of adenosine-5'-triphosphate (ATP). We have previously reported supramolecular assembly of a chemically modified GroEL to form 1D nanotube architectures with or without encapsulated artificial guests.² Very recently, we incorporated DNA strands to apical domains of GroEL (^{DNA}GroEL) and fabricated a new version of GroEL nanotube by the DNA hybridization methods.^{3,4} In the present study, we utilized ^{DNA}GroEL to immobilize on to a DNA-appended AuNP (^{DNA}AuNP). The formation of GroEL-functionalized AuNP (^{GroEL}AuNP) was confirmed by light scattering, electron microscopy and Zeta potential measurements. Interestingly, the GroELs on ^{GroEL}AuNP shows ATPase activity comparable to that of unattached GroEL, demonstrating the intact nature of biomolecular machine on AuNP surface.⁵ Further, a second layer of GroEL with complementary DNA to the first layer was grafted onto the ^{GroEL}AuNP (Figure 1), holding the promise of using it as a building blocks for the construction of hierarchical hybrid architectures.

Figure 1. Scheme showing the strategies for GroEL immobilization onto a AuNP and the formation of a second layer of GroEL.

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Numerical and Experimental Investigation of Slow-Drift Damping for a Single-Point Moored Floating Offshore Wind Turbine

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In recent years, Floating Offshore Wind Turbines (i.e FOWTs) have been attracting attention as a power generation method suitable for Japan waters, having few shallow coastlines and steep seabed topography. However, FOWTs have not been commercialized in Japan, the primary reason being high installation and maintenance costs. Single-Point Mooring (SPM) method is one of the measures to solve these problems. SPM is a mooring method in which the mooring points of the floating body are combined into single point. When the wind blows, the floating wind turbine follows the wind and turn around the moored point facing the wind. Therefore, the yaw control system can be eliminated leading to reduced costs.

However, SPM-FOWTs poses new challenges such as wind tracking performance and slow-drift motion, which are unexplored. In this study, an attempt is made to investigate the slow-drift damping phenomenon of a new-type FOWT moored by SPM system. Real-Time Hybrid Model (ReaTHM) testing is conducted on a 1/60 scale model and slow-drift motion about the moored point is observed. Forced yawing test is carried out on a 1/200 scale model to obtain a database of slow-drift damping force coefficient. A time-history simulation code is developed to incorporate the slow-drift motion response on the wind turbine. Two cases of simulation, one with slow-drift damping and another without slow-drift damping are carried out. Comparing the experimental and simulation results, it is revealed that the simulation with slow-drift damping coefficient predicts the motion response phenomenon better than the simulation without slow-drift damping coefficient. It is concluded that slow-drift damping is an important factor while simulating the turning motion about the moored point.

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Experiments and Numerical Analysis on Wave Energy Converter using Ocean Breaking Waves

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The ocean contains a huge amount of extractable energy within which must be harnessed in a meaningful way as it remains a challenging task owing to the erratic nature of sea waves, currents, and uncontrollable sea states. To harness the power of breaking waves on the seashore, a new type of wave energy converter has been studied at Okinawa Institute of Science and Technology Graduate University (OIST) since 2014. When waves approaching the shoreline steepen owing to decreased sea depth, wave energy condensation at the surface occurs. Before breaking in the surf zone, a steepened wave achieves the critical velocity of 4-8 m/sec shoreward. A rotating blade uses breaking characteristics in the surf zone to convert wave energy into power.

The work presents an experimental and numerical investigation of computational study on a prototype model of a wave energy device. The turbine having five blades of variable chord lengths, twist angles, and constant thickness profile was tested under similar flow as well as testing conditions. which would help characterize the turbine performance. The validation performed for different test cases showed that the present numerical results match in good agreement with the experimental results.

Keywords: Wave Energy Converter; Breaking wave; Computational Fluid Dynamics; Turbine and Generator characteristics, Experimental Analysis, Numerical Analysis

Accurate classification of breast cancer cells from normal mammary epithelial cells by machine learning assisted Raman microspectroscopy

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Histopathology is generally considered a ‘Gold Standard’ in diagnosis of cancers. But it is invasive and time consuming. Moreover, it may not be easy to perform biopsy in many situations. Therefore cytology-based non-invasive diagnosis is recommended. Cytodiagnosis of cancers is normally done by staining and observing cellular morphology under the optical microscope. However, conventional cytology suffers from low sensitivity and specificity. This makes definitive diagnosis difficult. There is a need to develop alternative technologies for reliable cytodiagnosis. Here we propose a new non-invasive, label-free diagnostic technique using Raman spectroscopy and machine learning. In this study, we demonstrate discrimination

Figure SEQ Figure \^* ARABIC 1. Average Raman spectra of HMEpC and MCF7 cells (A), intensity ratios of DNA/Lipid (B) and Protein/Lipid (C) with corresponding ‘p’ values.

of breast cancer cells (MCF-7) from normal human mammary epithelial cells (HMEpC).

Averaged Raman spectra obtained from 30 independent MCF-7 and HMEpC cells are shown in Figure 1A. It is known that cancer cells are rapidly dividing and hence we made a fairly safe assumption that ratios of biomolecules may be a potential marker of cancers. First, Raman bands at 1440 (Lipid), 1003 (protein) and 786 (DNA) were used to calculate ratios such as DNA / Lipid and Protein / Lipid by univariate method (analyzing one band at a time). There is a marked difference in ratios of DNA/Lipids (Figure 1B) and Protein/Lipids (Figure 1C). However, this procedure is ambiguous as multiple components may contribute to each band. So, advanced multivariate statistics such as PCA, LDA, SVM and neural networks were utilized to discriminate cancer cells successfully. However, the molecular basis is not established by any of these methods. Therefore, we employed multivariate curve resolution analysis (MCR) to analyze full spectral region and separated pure biomolecular components that are responsible for objective classification [1]. Combined results from MCR analysis and neural networks shine light on the molecular origin for reliable discrimination and opens up new possibilities in diagnosis and treatment of breast cancers.

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Session 3A

Young Researchers

(Short presentations)

Cell Surface Engineering with Functional Peptides to Improve Therapeutic Effect for Stroke Treatment

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Stroke related disorders are currently seeking cell-based therapies to help in protection of infarct area. However, none of the therapies can get clinical acceptance due to lack of efficacy data, heterogeneity of cell populations and low scale clinical trials. In this study we used iPSCs (induced pluripotent stem cells) derived neural progenitor cells (NPCs) because of their higher availability, neural lineage, and homogenous behavior. During a stroke, there is an activation of endothelial cells which leads to the upregulation of adhesion molecules such as E-selectin, ICAM-1, VCAM-1 etc. We have developed a material for modifying the cells' surface such that they specifically bind to E-selectin. The material is a conjugation of three components, a peptide which is complementary to the activated endothelial cells, PEG (poly (ethylene glycol)) to help the cells in evading immune system, and lipid for the incorporation of this conjugate on the cells. We studied the binding of the conjugate to e-selectin molecules, as well binding of the modified cells to e-selectin expressing cells. We also monitored the cells over a period of 7 days to see if there is any change in viability or genetic make-up of the cells. As hypothesized, there was no adverse effect on the cells after modification. Furthermore, a cell-binding assay with immobilized E-selectin surface as well as activated endothelium was performed to study the localization of these cells. We were successful in obtaining modified neural progenitor cells which bind to e-selectin and e-selectin overexpressing cells, which can be used for transplantation in inflammatory disorders.

How can we maintain the “Richness” of agriculture? Focus upon the Utilization and protection of heirloom crops in Shizuoka

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The way in which “Shizuoka Forum of Heirloom Crops”, established in 2013, have enhanced our society’s economic, historical, and cultural “richness” shall be the main focus of this case study. The crops that we analyzed are indigenous crops, otherwise known as “Heirloom Crops”.

In this research, at least 55 different kinds of crops were confirmed to have survived in Shizuoka Prefecture. However, it is debatable as to what geographic and social boundaries should be counted as a unit. Five major issues were found. First, farmers themselves cultivate without any particular recognition, so they are dependent upon individuals and have no sense of inheritance. Second, the technique of selecting and preserving good seeds, "an eye for selecting good seeds," is likely to die out because it can be replaced by modern varieties of the same type that can be substituted after paying money. Third, the technology of cultivation methods adapted to the natural and social environment is difficult to sustain due to environmental changes. Fourth, limited small-scale distribution, such as home consumption and distribution to neighbors, has supported the use of indigenous crops. Finally, cultural contexts such as seasonal cooking and festival rituals have sustained the specific uses of these crops.

The issues indicate that there are three sources of “richness” of agriculture. The first is the various intrinsic values found in the surrounding environment and human activities, including the socio-cultural values created in the relationship between crops and people, such as the "landscape with heirloom crops". The second is that those values will be passed on to future generations, and what has been passed down from the past to the present will lead to the future, and great energy can be gained from them. Third, these value headings and intergenerational inheritances can be self-directed by local communities. The "richness" of agriculture other than its economic value is linked to its land and history. It is significant that those who share the land and history can maintain the value of agriculture autonomously.

Covid-19 impact on Collaboration between University Students and Local Community

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In recent years, a sequence of community-university cooperation activities has been promoted by the Japanese government. Students from Tokai University implement the "Mochimune Seminar" as one of the collaborative activities. The seminar run by students of Tokai University, has been continuously integrating into the festival of "Mochimune" area in Shizuoka since 2014. However, the influence of COVID-19 depresses this activity, hence the student group must explore alternative methods to continue the project implementation. In this study, we conducted an activity review and an interview survey with leaders of the student group to propose new methodologies. In addition, the presenter has also participated in this activity as one of the members from 2019.

This research revealed that four issues are confronting the seminar. Firstly, the festival was canceled due to the COVID-19 pandemic, which made it possible to achieve the goal of energizing the community through participation in the festival. Secondly, the seminar became virtual, making it difficult to communicate. Thirdly, the university festival conducted virtually, making it difficult for university students to have mutual trust. Lastly, Collaboration with the local community stagnated. From these issues, it become clear that the activities of the seminar depended on the festival activities and did not have any other means.

It was suggested that the above issues had occurred before COVID-19 pandemic. Thus, we expect we can further develop our activities after the pandemic by conducting the reality checks which became customary practice during the pandemic and seeking ways forward to improve them.

Evaluation of the carotenoid contents heirloom sweet potato 'ninjin-imo'

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There are at least 55 heirloom crops grown in Shizuoka Prefecture today. The cultivation of sweet potatoes spread from Omaezaki city (Shizuoka) to the west along the coast. The heirloom variety of sweet potato, 'ninjin-imo' with the root mass of color like a carrot, has a unique texture and flavor. Therefore, ninjin-imo is often used as a dried sweet potato. We have reported that the β -carotene content of this variety is extremely high compared to commercial varieties. In the present study, several sweet potato strains including 'ninjin-imo' were grown in the field of the Faculty of Agriculture, Shizuoka University from 2014 to 2020. Carotenoids were extracted from the various samples using a solvent and quantified year to year by HPLC to total carotenoid content. In 2019 and 2020, samples processed into dried sweet potatoes were also analyzed.

The total carotenoid content was the highest in 'ninjin-imo' (Kakegawa) in all the years. β -carotene accounted for more than 90% of total carotenoids (β -carotene, β -cryptoxanthin, lutein, All-trans-violaxanthin and 9-cis-violaxanthin) in any year. From this result, it was clarified that 'ninjin-imo' (Kakegawa) has a feature of containing the β -carotene, which is a factor that determines the total carotenoid content in the roots of sweet potato mass.

At present, the heirloom sweet potato variety 'ninjin-imo' (Kakegawa) is cultivated locally by a small number of farmers. From the results over time, 'ninjin-imo' (Kakegawa) was confirmed to contain a nutritional property, especially a large amount of β -carotene compared to commercial varieties. It was suggested that the functional properties of β -carotene of 'ninjin-imo' may lead to its future utilization and conservation.

Mortaparib^{mild}: A Novel Anticancer Agent with p53-dependent and -independent Mechanism

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Cancer is a highly heterogenous disease characterized by the uncontrolled proliferation of abnormal cells in the body, involving multiple mechanisms responsible for its progression. The tumor suppressor protein p53 is frequently mutated or functionally inactivated in a large variety of cancers. Its inactivation by mortalin, a member of the heat shock 70 protein family overexpressed in many types of cancer, has been shown to implicate in carcinogenesis. Therefore, inhibition of mortalin-p53 interaction by natural and synthetic compounds has emerged as a rational cancer therapeutic strategy. We identified a novel triazole derivative 4-[(4-amino-5-thiophen-2-yl-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)sulfanylmethyl]-N-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1,3-thiazol-2-amine from our chemical library screening based on the imaging of mortalin-p53 interaction disruption. Validation of anticancer potential of this molecule, named Mortaparib^{mild}, in a variety of human cancer cells was performed by bioinformatics and experimental analyses. Mortaparib^{mild} is a novel compound that could bind to mortalin and p53 on their interaction sites. It caused downregulation of mortalin and PARP1 expression in cancer cells. It was also effective for triggering apoptosis/growth arrest in p53^{null} cancer cells suggesting its p53-independent activities. Molecular characterization of the anticancer activity of Mortaparib^{mild} upon its p53-dependent and/or independent mechanism will be discussed.

Isolation and Characterization of 3-Chlorobenzoate (3-CB) Degrading Bacteria from Soils in Shizuoka

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The chlorinated aromatic compounds are toxic to various organisms and persist in the environment for a long time. Microbial degradations of chlorinated aromatic compounds are usually catabolized by aromatic ring hydroxylating dioxygenases converting the substrates into simpler intermediates, which are always chlorocatechols in ortho cleavage pathway. However, there is a growing need to identify microbes with catabolic potentials to degrade the compound. This research was conducted to identify bacteria with functional catabolic genes. In this study, 22 bacterial strains degrading 3-chlorobenzoate (3-CBA) were isolated from soils around Shizuoka city in Japan. The isolates were identified as members of *Betaproteobacteria*; *Burkholderiaceae* family based on their 16S rRNA gene sequences. Whole genome sequencing of six isolates were determined and then their putative catabolic gene clusters were compared with the well-characterized 3-CBA degradative gene cluster (*tfdTCDEF*) of *Burkholderia* sp. strain NK8. Five isolates, *Paraburkholderia hospital* 19CS91, *Paraburkholderia terrae* 19C8, *Burkholderia novacaledonica* 19CS11, *Burkholderia novacaledonica* 19CS22 *Burkholderia novacaledonica* 19CS42 possessed similar gene clusters with that of strain NK8 in their chromosomes. The NK8-type catabolic genes have been rarely found, and now the features of these degraders were compared.

Keywords: Degradation, Chlorocatechol *ortho*-cleavage pathway, 3-Chlorobenzoic acid (3-CBA), Chlorocatechol

Fig: Degradation pathway of chlorinated aromatic compounds via chlorocatechol modified *ortho*-cleavage pathway.

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Stress Buffering and Longevity Effects of AE in *Caenorhabditis elegans* (*C. elegans*)

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Purpose: Stress-induced depression and anxiety are rampantly increasing due to the demands of this fast-paced world. AE, a promising nutraceutical, was historically used in wound healing and stress relieving. Unfortunately, there is no concrete scientific evidence backing these claims. In this study, the stress buffering and longevity effects of AE in *Caenorhabditis elegans* (*C. elegans*) was investigated.

Methods: Worms were treated with or without AE in standard *E. coli* OP50 food. The effect of AE on the longevity, healthspan (reproduction, body length, motility) and survival under stress (heat and oxidative) was determined. Also, cortisol and oxytocin levels, accumulated fat and reactive oxygen species (ROS) levels, gene expressions in green fluorescence protein (GFP) tagged worms and at mRNA levels were examined. Finally, oxidative stress tolerance of mutant worms was studied to determine molecular pathways that may be involved in AE-mediated activity.

Results: AE improved healthspan and lifespan of both normal and stressed worms. Cortisol levels reduced while oxytocin, increased. Notably, AE decreased fat accumulation and ROS in vivo but failed to show in vitro antioxidant ability. AE further increased the nuclear accumulation of DAF-16::GFP and GFP expressions of *hsp-16.2*, *sod-3* and *gst-4*. Similarly, mRNA levels of these genes were upregulated in addition to that of *hsp-70*, *ctl-1*, and *myo-3* genes. Finally, AE treatment failed to increase the survival of *daf-16* and *skn-1* mutant depicting its activity depended on these genes possibly via the IIS pathway.

Conclusion: Evidently, relieves stress and enhances longevity via the collective activities of *daf-16*, heat shock proteins, antioxidant genes and hormonal regulation. AE may be a potent nutraceutical for relieving stress.

Keywords: *C. elegans*, Anti-stress, Anti-aging, Antioxidant, stress hormones

Developing a Low-Cost Open-Source based UAV System for Mapping of Plantations Land Use in Sabah, Malaysian Borneo.

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The low-cost and open-source Unmanned Aerial Vehicle Systems segment is becoming an important remote sensing alternative for assisting sustainable plantation management both for industrial and smallholders. The high-resolution imagery acquired from UAVs are feasible for the identification of land use types and mapping at a local scale. This greatly reduces the operational costs while leveraging the potential of UAV applications for plantations. In this study we demonstrated the development of UAV and mapping workflow for tropical plantations. We built a DIY flying wing type UAV platform propelled by an electric motor propulsion system from hobby-grade parts. The UAV was powered using a LiPo battery and was controlled using open-source autopilot system and mission planning software. A consumer grade RGB camera was modified and programmed specifically for collecting the aerial photos. We collected aerial photos processed it using open-sourced Structure from Motion (SfM) software and was analyzed in GIS software. The SfM allowed a 3D model reconstruction of the study area which outputs were Digital Surface Model (DSM), Orthomosaic and point clouds. These were useful for estimating biophysical parameters of the plantations such as the tree cover, height, canopy size and canopy gaps in the plantations. Detailed land use information derived from the SfM outputs are very useful to help plantation owners to make an informed management decisions. This low-cost workflow can make the benefits of aerial imagery-based plantation management accessible to low-income small holder communities. The open-source and simple workflow can be replicated by researcher for mapping of other plantations areas.

Isolation and Identification of Indigenous Chromium Tolerant Bacteria from a Heavy Metal Polluted Urban Creek, India

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Uncontrolled discharge of industrial effluents and wastewaters has resulted in a significant increase in Hexavalent Chromium Cr(VI) levels in urban rivers and tidal inlets such as Mumbai's Versova Creek. Mechanical removal of such heavy metals is both expensive and time-consuming. Indigenous bacteria' ability to bioremediate Cr(VI) could be a viable option. In this study, six indigenous bacteria were isolated from the sediments of Versova Creek and that were capable of tolerating Cr(VI) up to 2000 ppm. They belonged to the genera *Bacillus* and *Pseudomonas* as confirmed from the 16S rRNA sequencing. The in-vitro metal removing capacity of the pure cultures ranged from 90% - 96% when the culture medium (pH 7.0) was supplemented with 400 ppm of Cr(VI) and incubated at 37°C. The isolates were also tested for bioflocculant synthesis for bioflocculant assisted Cr(VI) biosorption, two of the isolates (AKVCRR04 and AKVCRR05) showed high flocculation activity 89.75 and 89.88% respectively by the 5th day of incubation. The growth profile of isolates and final pH with respect to the flocculation activity assay revealed bioflocculant production to peak either during or in the late stationary phase. These bacteria highly tolerant to Cr(VI) have significant potential for Cr(VI) biosorption and removal/ detoxification from contaminated sites such as Versova creek.

Session 3B

Young Researchers

(Short presentations)

microRNA-708 Regulates CARF (a stress regulatory protein) Differentially in Telomerase Positive and Negative Human Cancer Cells

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A large majority of cancer cells are marked by activation of an enzyme called telomerase that causes maintenance of telomere length. However, some cancer cells lack activation of telomerase and possess alternative mechanism to maintain their telomeres called ALT. Molecular mechanisms of switching on of telomerase or ALT are not clearly understood. We hypothesized that these mechanisms may involve noncoding microRNAs and conducted microRNA array analysis on isogenic telomerase-positive (TEP) and telomerase-negative (ALT) cancer cell lines. Amongst nine miRNAs that showed difference in their expression in TEP and ALT cancer cells, microRNA-708 (miR-708) was consistently highly expressed in a large panel of ALT cells. Extensive molecular analyses of cancer cell phenotypes revealed that miR-708 is a tumor suppressor miR. Its overexpression induced suppression of cell migration, invasion, and angiogenesis in both TEP and ALT cells. Of note, it caused inhibition of cell proliferation only in TEP cells suggesting that ALT cells have acquired the ability to escape inhibition of cell proliferation by sustained miR-708 overexpression. We report that miR-708 targets CARF protein, involved in dual regulation of DNA damage and stress-regulatory signaling, endorsing association of these pathways with carcinogenesis. Furthermore, it is suggested that TEP and ALT cells may differ in their CARF-mediated stress response and hence should also be considered for cancer therapeutics.

Antistress and Antiaging Activities in Lipoic Acid: Experimental Evidence

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Cultured living cells respond to stress (an external stimuli that is perceived as undesired) by evoking adaptations in biochemical and metabolic pathways. Stressed cells can be identified by their altered morphology and underlying molecular signaling pathways determined by upregulation/downregulation of gene expression as compared to the state of homeostasis determining the normal functioning of cells.

Such stress induced changes in gene expression and cell functions can be monitored by using a variety of *in vitro* cell culture and molecular assays. Chronic stresses have been related to several pathologies including, cancer, premature aging and neurodegenerative diseases. Oxidation of macromolecules and accumulation of molecular garbage have been assigned as one of the major causes underlying these ailments. In view of this, we anticipated that lipoic acid (a naturally occurring fatty acid found in yeast, spinach, broccoli and organ meats such as liver and kidney and reported to have good antioxidant properties) may be useful in managing stress and stress-related ailments. We investigated the effect of two alpha-lipoic acid (ALA) enantiomers, R-ALA and S-ALA on stressed cells in culture. While R-ALA is one of the natural essential cofactor of the mitochondrial-based cell oxidative machinery, S-ALA is its optical by-product. We report that R-ALA/S-ALA were relatively non-toxic to U2OS (human osteosarcoma) cells. Cells cultured in R-ALA/S-ALA supplemented medium showed protection against heavy metal (sodium arsenite), heat and oxidative (hydrogen peroxide) stresses. Furthermore, induction of pro-hypoxia signaling and differentiation of brain-derived cells were observed that may support the clinical use of these compounds for treatment of Alzheimers' disease and high-altitude sickness. These data propose lipoic acid as a potential ingredient of anti-aging and anti-stress health supplements and hence warrants further attention in laboratory and clinical studies.

Anti-Stress Activities in the Hypoxia-Inducing Phytochemical Tectorigenin

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Moderate amounts of hypoxia is known to induce anti-stress mechanisms in cells that may potentially prevent and/or reverse some neurodegenerative disorders, caused by oxidative stress and accumulation of molecular garbage. Tectorigenin is obtained from leopard lilly or *Iris domestica*. It is known to possess strong antioxidant properties and has been widely used in traditional medicine as a treatment for inflammatory disorders of the lungs. To find natural drugs with hypoxia-modulating potential, we carried out a screening using Hypoxia Inducing Factor-1 α driven by luciferase as a reporter and identified ‘tectorigenin’ as one of the hypoxia-inducing phytochemicals. We performed dose-dependent cytotoxicity assays, short-term and long-term cell-viability, migration and differentiation assays to characterise the activities of the drug. Tectorigenin has found to be non-toxic within the dose range of 1-10 μ M. Cells subjected to nontoxic doses showed dose-dependent increase in cell migration. Wound healing assays demonstrated the consistency to its identification as a pro-hypoxia factor. Brain-derived glioblastoma cancer cells when treated with nontoxic doses of tectorigenin showed glial differentiation phenotype. Cellular and molecular analyses revealed that tectorigenin is broadly nontoxic and mimics the hypoxia signalling induced by cobalt chloride, a standard hypoxia-inducer used in laboratory, but is limited by its toxicity to the cells. Based on this data, we propose the use of tectorigenin to induce hypoxia in laboratory studies, and to manage hypoxia-driven ailments, such as neurodegenerative disorders and high-altitude sickness. Further studies are warranted to support these claims and to dissect their molecular mechanism(s) of action.

Mortaparib^{Plus} - A Novel Multimodal Anticancer Small Molecule

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The tumor suppressor protein p53 plays a fundamental role in tumor suppression through the cell cycle arrest and apoptosis mechanisms. In cancer cells, Mortalin, a member of the hsp70 protein family, interacts with p53 in the cell cytoplasm and nucleus resulting in an inactivation of its transcriptional activation function. The inhibition of mortalin-p53 interaction and a subsequential reactivation of p53's tumor suppression function has been proposed as a possible approach for the identification and development of novel anticancer drug candidates.

A screening of a high-content chemical library was performed in order to search for a molecule with mortalin-p53 interaction disrupting characteristics. After four rounds of visual assays for mortalin and p53, we discovered a triazole derivative (4-[(1E)-2-(2-phenylindol-3-yl)-1-azavinyl]-1,2,4-triazole, named Mortaparib^{Plus}) with a potential ability to disrupt mortalin-p53-complex. To validate the activity of this novel molecule, we recruited two types of colorectal cancer [HCT116 and DLD-1] cells and breast cancer [MCF-7 and T47D] cells with varying status of p53 protein.

Bioinformatics analyses showed that the Mortaparib^{Plus} has the ability to completely inhibit the formation of mortalin-p53 complex. Immunoprecipitation analyses revealed that it indeed abrogates the mortalin-p53 complex formation and cause growth arrest/apoptosis through various mechanisms (inhibition of PARP1, up-regulation of p73, downregulation of mortalin and CARF proteins) in HCT116, DLD-1, and MCF-7 cells. Furthermore, Mortaparib^{Plus} caused metabolic stress in T47D cells. Mortaparib^{Plus} is proposed as a potential multimodal small molecule for cancer treatment that requires further extensive laboratory and clinical studies.

Cell-based Screenings for Anti-stress Natural Compounds: Selection of Ashwagandha Withanolides and Their Molecular Mechanisms

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Stress is an inevitable component of life and has been established as a causative factor for accelerated biological aging and several diseases such as cancer, neurodegeneration, and muscle-related dysfunctions. Cultured cells show molecular stress responses similar to those occurring at the tissue and organismic level. In this study, we undertook cell-based screening for natural compounds possessing anti-oxidative stress activity. Cells were subjected to oxidative stress by exposure to paraquat; the compounds that resulted in protection (as measured by cell viability assays) against paraquat stress were selected and investigated for their potential for anti-heavy metal and anti-hypoxia stresses induced by cadmium chloride and cobalt chloride, respectively. The compounds that reduced cell death induced by these three kinds of stresses were selected. Molecular mechanism of stress protection was investigated by a variety of cell-based molecular assays. The three sets of stresses caused reduction in cell viability that was significantly inhibited by Ashwagandha withanolides and extracts. Molecular assays revealed increase in (i) DNA double-strand damage (ii) ROS accumulation and (iii) protein aggregation in stressed cells, and was prevented to a large extent in cells treated with Ashwagandha extracts and withanolides. Decrease in mitochondrial membrane potential in the stressed cells was recovered in the treated cells. Furthermore, Ashwagandha extract treated brain- and muscle-derived cells showed strong differentiation as marked by the respective differentiated cell morphology and the expression of neurodifferentiation markers. Taken together, the study strongly suggested anti-stress and pro-differentiation potential of Ashwagandha extracts that may be recruited of management of stress and old age-related ailments.

Use of sequencing batch reactor for simultaneous carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus removal from domestic wastewater by alternating cycle times

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The discharge of nutrients rich wastewater to aquatic ecosystem results in eutrophication problem. In doctoral study, the construction of a bench sequencing batch reactor (SBR) for simultaneous nitrification and denitrification (SND) and phosphorus removal will be investigate for simultaneous organic carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus removal from domestic wastewater. At beginning, reactor will be optimized for optimum cycle time with different sequences of anaerobic, aerobic and anoxic phases by varying hydraulic retention time (HRT) and volume exchange ratios (VER) for higher removal of chemical oxygen demand (COD), ammonia nitrogen (NH₃-N), nitrate (NO₃-N) and total phosphorus (TP) using synthetic waste water.

To prepare the synthetic wastewater, characterization of local municipal wastewater is prerequisite as it will define the limits of COD, NH₃-N, PO₄³⁻ content of target wastewater. In this presentation, we intent to present the municipal wastewater characteristics of Varanasi city. Verification of SBR experiment set-up will also be shown to demonstrate the performance of experiment set-up.

In future, optimum retention time would be determined using statistical analysis also known as ANOVA. The effect of influent carbon to nitrogen ratio (C/N) on the removal performance of advanced N and P will also be studied.

Geospatial assessment of expanding solar farms for electrification of India

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Renewable energy sectors are expanding in unprecedented rate nationwide, putting stresses on land resources. Solar energy plants are most prominent form of energy source and appropriate siting of farms could help mitigate existing land-based economy and ecosystem services implementation compromises. This involves land use and energy planning to ensure minimum negative impact on the environment. As of December 2019, India reached around 34 GW of solar installations. It has set a huge target of establishing 100GW power by year 2022, further achieving 280GW generation capacity by 2030. It is important to have an analytical assessment of placements of solar farms, as it can bring long term change in current environmental landcover. Consequently imposing additional resource demand for effective working of plants. Huge amount of water is required for smooth running of powerplants, and of all the sources 60% comes from groundwater while rest from surface water. Google Earth Engine was crucial in analyzing and mapping solar farms across the country. Nighttime light VIIRS (Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometric Suite) data was vital for assessing electrification of India. To fulfill India's target of 280GW renewable energy through solar power, an estimate of 1 million hectares of land is required.

Machine learning based approach for assessment of typhoon induced forest damage in case of Hokkaido

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Climate change induced warming oceans and sea level rise intensified the typhoonal activities, and have had widespread impacts on terrestrial ecosystems. Tree mortality and forest destruction during typhoon landfalls are important adverse impacts closely linked to terrestrial processes. Due to the sporadic nature of typhoons, evaluating their effects on forest ecosystem is often challenging. Here in this paper, we compared the utility of multiple vegetation damage estimation techniques using publicly accessible Landsat 8 images. We considered Hokkaido region of northern Japan as a case example, where three typhoons successively struck in 2016 and caused widespread forest destruction. Following indices including Disaster Vegetation Damage Index (DVDI), Difference Normalized difference vegetation index (DNDVI), Enhanced Vegetation Index (Δ EVI), and machine learning models such as Random Forest and Support Vector Machine classifiers with different training data; and the CLASlite software with built-in methods were used to detect the forest disturbance. Our results show that machine learning classifiers obtained the highest damage assessment accuracy but are also most computationally intensive and technically complex to implement. Both Random Forest (AUC = 0.77 – 0.80, ACC = 80.36%) and Support Vector Machines (AUC = 0.75 – 0.79, ACC = 80.36%) gave highest accuracies when using Fractional Vegetation Cover as input variable. Among the vegetation damage indices, DNDVI produced the highest accuracy (AUC= 0.775, ACC = 77.68%). CLASlite's forest disturbance classification gave conservative damage estimates (AUC = 0.77, ACC = 76.95%) but was easy to implement and had classification accuracy similar to the other methods. We also investigated the influence of the terrain characteristics and typhoon path on forest damage by analyzing topographic parameters (windwardness, wind exposition, elevation, slope, and distance from the typhoon path). Maximum damages were occurred on the windward side that exposed forest patches. Forest damage peaked at the highest elevations in the study area, possibly representing exposed hilltops. Methods and results presented in this study can be implemented as a framework for effective tool for stakeholders to monitor forest damages in response to increasing typhoon frequency in Asian region.

Capturing and transmission of drug resistance gene by conjugative plasmids

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The dissemination of antibiotic resistance genes among bacteria often occurs through the spreads of plasmids. We collected drug resistance plasmids from the river sediments of Tama River in Tokyo and wastewater plant (WWTP) in Japan. Five of them were identified as incompatibility group N (IncN) plasmids carrying antibiotic resistance genes. IncN plasmids have been known as self-transmissible plasmids found in *Enterobacteriaceae*. These plasmids have resistance genes against many antimicrobial classes including extended-spectrum betalactams, aminoglycosides, sulphonamides, tetracyclines and streptomycin. These plasmids were considered to have broad host range, but it has not necessarily been clearly shown. The objective of the present study is therefore investigation of the host range of the IncN plasmids. Filter mating assays were performed with a donor of IncN plasmid pMNCF070 with bacterial mixture containing strains of *Alphaproteobacteria*, *Betaproteobacteria* and *Gammaproteobacteria*. As a result, the plasmid could be transferred not only to the strains of *Gammaproteobacteria* but also to the strains of *Betaproteobacteria*. Now the transfer frequency of the plasmids are being compared.

Keywords: IncN, BHR, antimicrobial resistance gene, WWTP, GFP

Number	Plasmid name	Isolated sources	Size	GC (%)	Antibiotic Resistance Genes (ARG)
1.	pMNCF070	Active Sludge	39,426 bp	51.6	tet
2.	pMNBM072	River Sediment (Tamagawa)	55,403 bp	52.5	aac(6)-Ib-cr, rifampin ADP-ribosyltransferase, DfrA27, aadA16, ethidium bromide resistance protein, sul1, qnrB19
3.	pMNCF075	Active Sludge	49,079 bp	51.5	blaTEM-1, tetA, sulII, strA, strB
4.	pMNCF091	Active Sludge	67,562 bp	52.3	fosA3, sulII, strA, strB, , QnrS1, tetA, dfrA16
5.	pMNCF092	Active Sludge	55,403 bp	52.5	aac(6)-Ib-cr, rifampin ADP-ribosyltransferase, DfrA27, aadA16, ethidium bromide resistance protein, sul1, qnrB19

Study of Geo-morphological changes in Chambal Ravine of India using TanDEM-X SAR and machine learning model.

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Gully erosion mapping and monitoring is a very crucial part of land restoration or ravine reclamation projects. The main objective of this study is the assessment of morphological changes that occurred in the lower Chambal ravines of India from the year 2012 to 2017 by making gully erosion susceptibility map and volume estimation map with the help of GIS tools and Random Forest (RF) machine learning. The morphological and hydrological factors of the area were derived from InSAR DEM with the help of ArcGIS, SAGA-GIS, Google Earth Engine (GEE), and Google Earth (GE). The factors are used to prepare the training model, validation model, and supplied set by employing Random Forest. The accuracy of the model in terms of ROC value came up to 0.821. After validation, the training model was applied on the testing area for gully erosion susceptibility and volume change estimation mapping. The model predicted the 48.69 km² of the area is highly affected by gully erosion and other parts of the area have also significantly eroded by the gullying process. The volume of the area is also changed due to gully erosion. Furthermore, it was found as the presence of gully erosion in the Bhind region of central India is affecting the land actively which needs to be check and restore.

Keywords: Gully erosion susceptibility, Volume change estimation, machine learning model, Random Forest model.

Poster session
(Lunch time)

Two Snailfishes of the Genus *Osteodiscus* (Scorpaeniformes: Liparidae) from Japanese Waters

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Snailfishes of the family Liparidae are a morphologically diverse group of marine fishes, currently comprising about 32 genera with over 450 species worldwide. Occupying an unusually wide vertical habitat range, they are known from tidal pools to over 8,000 m depth. Members of Liparidae can be recognized by their tadpole-like shaped body, soft skin without scales, and variously shaped ventral sucking disk modified from pelvic fins. While many genera have been proposed, their phylogenetic relationships are so far largely uncertain.

The deep-water snailfish group *Osteodiscus* Stein 1978 is primarily distinguished from other genera by its reduced musculature pelvic disk covered only by thin skin. This genus was comprised three species *Osteodiscus cascadiae* Stein 1978, *Osteodiscus andriashevi* Pitruk and Fedorov 1990, and *Osteodiscus rhepostomias* Stein 2012 from the Pacific Ocean except Japanese waters. During the taxonomic examination of snailfishes deposited in the National Museum of Nature and Science (Tokyo, Japan), I discovered two specimens of *Osteodiscus* collected from off the Pacific coast of northern Japan. A specimen collected off Iwate at a depth about 2,000 m, was identified as *O. andriashevi* by its vertebral and fin ray counts, teeth and pectoral fin shape, and caudal skeleton morphology. Because *O. andriashevi* was previously known only from a limited area of the Sea of Okhotsk, my examined specimen represents the first Japanese record and the southernmost record of this species. The other specimen collected off Hokkaido at a depth about 4,700 m, was a new species *Osteodiscus abyssicola* Murasaki, Kai, Endo and Fukui 2021. It is distinguished from all currently recognized congeners by its vertebral and fin ray counts, teeth and pectoral fin shape, caudal skeleton morphology, cephalic pore and gill slit sizes, and anus position.

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Covid-19 impact on Collaboration between University Students and Local Community, Hiyori Nagano, Tokai university	Page 59
Evaluation of the carotenoid contents heirloom sweet potato ‘ninjin-imo’, Setsuko Maeda, Shizuoka Professional University of Agriculture	Page 60

Remote sensing in coastal water monitoring: Applications in the Suruga Bay and the coastal waters along the east coast of Japan

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Remote sensing/satellite observation of land and oceans is a field of research developed during the last quarter of the 20th century. Its importance is widely recognized because of the amount of information it provides to the scientific community and the general public. The outcomes of remote sensing/satellite observation can be used to address and study significant aspects of environmental concerns related to climate change. There is continuous improvement of the methods and means of remote sensing observations to achieve more accurate and helpful information. The present work is an effort to review the technologies used in remote sensing and the general applications comprehensively for scientists who do not specialize in this area of research. This work demonstrates a case study/application in the Suruga Bay (located close to the symposium venue), an interesting area influenced by the seasonal weather phenomena, the river discharges, and the Kuroshio Current. We underline the importance of the continuous monitoring of the coastal environment so that the stakeholders in the coastal areas can successfully manage this dynamic environment.

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